

**IN THEIR WORDS: A QUALITATIVE STUDY EXPLORING
BELONGINGNESS AND POSITIVE ACADEMIC OUTCOMES
FOR FIRST-GENERATION LATINX STUDENTS**

A Dissertation By

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Abstract:

This qualitative study asks first-generation Latinx students what they valued and appreciated in their White teachers throughout their K-12 school. This study highlights the voices and stories of the participants in their words.

Three conclusions are pulled from the analysis of data cultivated through empathy interviews: first-generation Latinx (FGL) students care far more about the demeanor of their teachers than the instructional practices and classroom policies they utilized; FGL students implore teachers to bring empathy, patience, compassion and understanding to students above all else; it is incumbent upon educational institutions to train White teachers with intention and purpose on how to incorporate students' culture, background and interests.

There are resulting implications for policy and practice. Purposeful attention to the identification and cultivation of preferred characteristics is needed. Hiring practices need to discern candidates who are more likely to bring these traits to the profession from the beginning. Principals need to incorporate professional development steeped in culturally relevant pedagogy and the student-centered approach of knowing students authentically. Principals need to be authorized to hold teachers accountable when they fail to treat diverse students with patience and understanding.

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And, to every student I have ever had the privilege to serve...this is yours too!

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Under the din of a cacophonous freeway, nine people attempt to coexist in an 800 square foot apartment. Two mattresses rest on the floor of the living room, bracketing a nearly empty mini fridge haloed by the notice of impending eviction taped to the wall above. While this is a literal description of a home visit I performed, it is painfully symbolic of the reality faced by thousands of students across the United States. Nominally affluent Orange County, California is not immune to this state of affairs; one such district, the East-West Unified School District (EWUSD, a pseudonym), is home to several pockets of poverty just like this.

One of the unintended consequences of capitalism—though many influential thinkers, such as Rawls and Piketty, argue this aspect is much more intentional than proponents want to admit—is the drastic accumulation of wealth by those few who tend to possess more resources to begin with (Vallier, 2019). This cycle is manifested almost viscerally in EWUSD when some students’ “guest room” is the same size as others’ entire living space. The purpose here is *not* to assign blame to those who are fortunate, as they did not choose their parentage any more than their poverty-stricken counterparts. It is, however, to highlight that our students are by no means coming to school with the same resources, backgrounds, experiences, knowledge, or support structures.

Both within and between schools in the United States, such disparities in different students’ material resources are a norm to be expected (Owens, 2018; Rothstein, 2019). Why then is anyone surprised when educational outcomes fall into completely predictable patterns, often directly correlated to household income or race (Duncan & Murnane, 2016; Papay et al., 2015)? And as important as it is not to conflate class issues with ethnicity issues, the reality is that in Orange County broadly, and in EWUSD specifically, the lines of poverty divide almost directly across ethnic lines. This casts non-white students—predominately Latinx in the example of this district—in the shadow of poverty, segregated geographically by literal railroad tracks and figuratively by the invisible barrier of low expectations.

In the end, making excuses for disparities is convenient and easy, but does not pave the way for genuine human progress. Both anecdotally and statistically, there have been many students from the unfortunate side of those tracks who have gone on to great academic and personal success. It is expedient to attribute individuals' "grit" as the sole factor in determining their triumphs, but like any good recipe, there are several essential ingredients that interact and combine to enhance the outcome (Duckworth, 2019). With an emphasis on those who are in the first generation of their family to pursue post-secondary education in this country, I strive to learn which ingredients are most potent, effective, and replicable in the effort to close both the opportunity and achievement gaps for low-income Latinx students in the EWUSD and beyond.

Background of the Problem

The notion that all students will (or even should) reach similar levels of academic achievement is noble, but unrealistic at best (Owens, 2018; Pfeffer, 2018). A cursory view of outcomes, either observationally through teacher experiences or tangibly through achievement data, shows that many different gaps exist between students based on gender, ethnicity, and socio-economic status. The most pernicious of these gaps is income-based, as it cuts across geography, gender, and family origin. For example, Murnane (2013) finds that the high school "graduation rate is 31% lower for children in the lowest SES quartile than for children in the top quartile." Strikingly, this chasm only grows wider when considering the University entrance requirements (Gurantz et al., 2017). While not a direct correlation, a vast proportion of Latinx students in the United States also fall into the lowest SES quartile, and even when disaggregated from the achievement data, they experience disproportionate academic outcomes and experience overrepresentation in exclusionary discipline (Benner & Graham, 2011; Farkas, 2003; Gándara & Contreras, 2009; Peguero & Shekarkhar, 2011; Skiba et al., 2011). Latinx students are also much less likely to have teachers who come from their same ethnic background, exacerbating the experience of unfair treatment and outcomes as well (Kohli & Pizarro, 2016).

A “fair” society relies upon an equal distribution of opportunity if it has any hope of a just and equitable distribution of resources and outcomes. For example, political philosopher John Rawls, in his examination of the international order titled *Law of Peoples* (1993), argues for rational actors to design policies and practices from an “original position” existing behind a “veil of ignorance (p. 30).” This positionality requires policies to be created without knowledge of the deciders’ characteristics, such as their race or gender, their abilities and tastes, as well as their wealth or position in society. Rawls argues that making decisions from this perspective leads to the creation of the most just and equitable distribution of *opportunity*. In its current form, our system of offering education to all students falls far short of such a fair distribution, and decisions are not behind made from behind any sort of “veil of ignorance.” Even when well-intentioned, the system provides opportunities that in and of themselves are not inherently equal based on what students and families can or cannot bring to bear in accessing such “bare opportunities” (Howe, 1997). Ostensibly the purveyors of public education aspire to the creation of a just, equitable, and inclusive environment for all students, but in practice fall short of such a reality.

Knowing that this problem is historical, political, perpetual, and ubiquitous, what can possibly be added that has not already been addressed? Some of the best research surrounding the drastic disparities in educational outcomes for students of poverty has shown pathways for progress. Numerous researchers have discovered the impact of teacher expectations on students, and how it can both help overcome or exacerbate a variety of circumstantial struggles (Friedrich, 2015; Rosenthal, 1987). Hattie (2009) has shown that “collective teacher efficacy” has a greater potential impact than even the direst home and neighborhood burdens. We know all these things, yet the same archetypical students continue to fall behind their financially stable peers—most often members of the dominant White culture—with a frustratingly predictable surety. Arguably, all students would benefit from discovering more concretely which enacted policies and practices are knocking down doors to equitable opportunity and successful outcomes in schools regardless of students’ circumstances.

An existing force for equity in schools across the United States, with a strong footprint in California broadly and EWUSD specifically, is the Advancement Via Individual Determination (AVID) program. The program's stated mission is to "close the achievement gap by preparing all students for college readiness and success in a global society," and those familiar with the philosophy know the strength of their emphasis on "*all*" (AVID Center). They exist to serve the student in the "middle" who is often left behind, with a specific focus on serving students who are historically underserved in secondary education and beyond (such as low-income, ethnic minority, and especially first-generation college bound), though they have made inroads into the elementary world as well. The AVID institution takes great pride in their collection of data, which overwhelmingly shows that students who are exposed to the AVID elective—with its specific pedagogical and philosophical practices—outperform all similar peer groups who do not have it. But, by their own definition, not "all" students qualify (or are appropriate) for the actual AVID elective class. What, then, is to be done for the vast numbers of students who would benefit from AVID policies and practices, but who do not qualify for or are not given the opportunity to participate in the actual elective?

It is worth noting, of course, that many Latinx students have found academic success and have broken cycles of poverty and social replacement. Scholarship around culturally relevant pedagogy (CRP) highlights the many ways in which Latinx students have overcome historical barriers and systemic obstacles to find parity in academic outcomes. When Latinx students feel welcomed and valued, for example, they tend to achieve more equitable outcomes (Garza, 2009; Perez, 2000). In addition, when teachers bring an asset-based mindset to what Latinx students bring with them to the classroom (i.e.: mastery of the Spanish language, collectivist view of their role as part of the group, commitment to family, strong work ethic), those students are likely to achieve in ways commensurate with their White peers (Perez, 2000; López, 2016).

Problem Statement

The problem that this study addresses is the persistence of unequal educational opportunities and outcomes for low-income Latinx students, with particular focus on those who are the first generation in their family pursue post-secondary education in the United States. As has been shown clearly and repeatedly, students who come from disadvantaged backgrounds—especially socio-economic struggles, which transcend nearly all other circumstances—will underperform academically (Coleman, 1988; Lareau, 2003; Portes & MacLeod, 1996). A common outcome of this underperformance is the perpetuation of the cycle of poverty (Gregg et al., 2019), with the ensuing generation simply replacing their parents' low-skill and low-wage employment, virtually guaranteeing that their children will face the same struggles, allowing the cycle to continue further. Without concrete, focused intervention, these families may continue to pay the very real human cost of lost opportunity, lost achievement, and lost prosperity for generations to come (Thiede & Brooks, 2018).

There is one known factor that provides cause for optimism in some cases. Existing research shows the profound impact of the AVID elective on first-generation college bound students. For example, according to the AVID Organization's official data for the senior class of 2017, 93% of AVID graduates complete college entrance requirements nationally, a rate far higher than their non-AVID peers (2018). Beyond high school, evidence also shows that AVID graduates outperform their equally challenged but non-AVID cohort as well as their contemporaries coming from privilege in their persistence rates in college, earning a degree at a rate four times that of their national peers (AVID, 2018).

While AVID data is promising, it is problematic for several reasons. First, not every school has an AVID program, even when their populations would benefit greatly. There are prohibitive costs associated with implementing the program, especially to fund teachers and AVID Tutors at a recommended 7:1 ratio. Secondly, there are philosophical concerns that may need to be overcome. A recent backlash against a college-going mentality for most students has led some to argue in favor of

career and technical education (CTE) as inherently in contrast to the pursuit of any traditional form of post-secondary education (Horn & Moesta, 2020). Third, even schools that have an AVID program cannot guarantee that every student who needs it is able to have a seat in an AVID elective. There may be too few sections, students may be misidentified and either admitted or omitted inappropriately, and scheduling conflicts abound for students who aspire to participate in various extracurricular activities.

More than any specific program, then, we must turn to those individuals who have been shown to have the most profound impact on students regardless of their station or circumstances: teachers. In a meta-analysis of the factors that lead to student success vis-à-vis “school belongingness,” Allen et al. (2016) discovered that “teacher support and positive personal characteristics were the strongest predictors of school belonging” and that such belonging had an overwhelmingly positive impact on student success. This comports directly with the mountain of evidence in favor of teachers being the pinnacle of potential positive impact on students during their school years and beyond (Chetty et al., 2014; Cantrell & Kane, 2013; Rockoff et al., 2011). While this data is encouraging and straightforward on the surface, more needs to be done to drill down and discover which teacher qualities and characteristics resonate with and improve outcomes for Latinx students generally, including those who are low-income or first-generation college-bound more specifically.

By looking at factors such as the impact of schoolwide AVID policies and practices, as well as the power of good teachers more broadly, perhaps it is possible to advance the search for an elusive “silver bullet” that can help solve the ceaseless inequities in opportunity and achievement for students suffering from poverty, an overwhelming majority of whom would be the first in their families to pursue post-secondary education. All educational practitioners could benefit from this knowledge, but site administrators and teachers would be able to implement such practices within schools, as well as hire for and develop such qualities within teachers in an effort to collectively improve the chances for as many students as possible to break the chains of poverty that have often enslaved their families for generations.

Purpose Statement

While it would be convenient to assume that simple quantitative data would illuminate the pursuit of solutions to this problem, research on teacher expectations and students' lived experiences suggests that valuable input also comes from qualitative investigations into how students themselves perceive aspects of their educational experience. Based on their unique lived experiences—and in their own words, using their own voices—they can tell us what they believe made the greatest impact. Ultimately, the purpose of this qualitative study was to discover if there are in fact qualities and characteristics of White educators that positively influence the degree of equitable educational attainment for those first-generation Latinx students who come from economic disadvantage. The sample for this research includes high school graduates from the classes of 2010-2020. The initial setting is the high school which serves the (geographically defined) specific pockets of low-income and predominantly Latinx families in EWUSD, but due to the sampling method it will also include first-generation Latinx students who attended high schools in other districts. Ultimately, I have seen improvement for large numbers of historically underserved students due to my own tireless dedication and love for my students, but I hope their stories can illuminate potential policies, practices, and behaviors that teachers across districts like EWUSD—and beyond—can tangibly implement to help change the world for their students.

An additional component to this study specifically is to home in on what White teachers in particular can do intentionally—both in policy and practice—to support students who come from different backgrounds than they do. Here, I will examine the perspectives of Latinx students, which is of importance not only in Southern California, but statewide and beyond as demographic shifts continue to evolve the tapestry of the American student body. One point to make for context is that, according to the most recent data from the California Department of Education, Latinx students make up 56.1% of the student body and White students comprise 20.1%; the most recent data on teacher ethnic breakdown shows that Latinx teachers only make up 21.1% of the teaching force whereas White teachers comprise

61.2% of teachers across the state (CDE, 2023). Here in Orange County, the disparity is even more stark: Latinx educators only represent 15.4% of teachers in Orange County, while Latinx students make up 47.9% of the student body; simultaneously, White teachers are 71.2% of the total pool, while White students make up only 22.5% of the total student population (CDE, 2023). The overwhelming majority of teachers who serve Latinx students do not come from the same background, culture, or perspectives. This study intends to discover what those teachers can do with intentionality to serve a population that may have dissimilar lived experiences.

Research Questions

In order to accomplish this purpose, I have posed the following research questions:

1. What personal qualities or characteristics do first generation Latinx students value most in their White teachers?
2. What classroom policies or practices do first generation Latinx students find beneficial when implemented by White teachers?

Significance

This research is important and will make a significant contribution to educational leadership because it will help pave the road for a more just, equitable and inclusive education for Latinx students whose voices have long been missing from the discussion surrounding impactful and effective teaching. Specifically, in highly segregated school districts like EWUSD, more needs to be done to provide increased opportunity and achievement for students and families on the margins, who want the same for their children as those other families with means on the other side of the proverbial—and in many districts, literal—tracks.

As we discover specific characteristics and practices that, according to the voices and stories of students themselves, can be shown to amplify the success of historically unsuccessful students who come from cultural marginalization and poverty, we can extend this insight to the vast and increasing numbers of Latinx students in schools across California and beyond.

School administrators can use evidence of effective practices to guide professional development (PD) and guide development of site level missions, visions, and practices so the rank-and-file teachers can equally employ such practices when looking for ways to increase success for their increasingly diverse student population. If the entire school team attempts to “paddle in the same direction” (here, in the form of reinforcing specific personal characteristics and implementing concrete pedagogical strategies campus wide), decisions will be guided by a common goal and will arguably be magnified through coherence, consistency, repetition and collective commitment. When an entire staff begins to live the creed that “all means all,” more students will benefit, and progress can be made on the long road to equity for students who come with limitations far outside of their control.

One point to acknowledge is to recognize the delimitations imposed by the nature of the study. I have chosen to begin my interviews with former students with whom I still have personal contact. This is a practical matter as much as anything else and will be a strong foundation upon which to expand beyond that participant pool using the “snowball sampling” method addressed more specifically in later chapters. In addition to that, I will be adhering to a script for the interviews; while there will be some organic interactions, the focus is intentional and topics that may be of interest to participants but that are not part of the predetermined interview protocol will not be included in this study. This also introduces some inherent limitations to the study as well; since my initial sample will come from students I know and have access to as their former high school teacher. This limits the starting pool to students known in the secondary setting; getting access to additional participants through the “snowball” method will be challenging. There are no guarantees as to participants’ willingness to participate, making it possible that the pool of interviewees will not be equally distributed between known and unknown participants. In an attempt to increase validity, I am trusting students’ memories of their K-12 school experience. I have acknowledged that the passage of time makes responses from memory not only less reliable from a simple memory standpoint, but the participants’ degree of awareness and understanding of what I am asking them was limited at best due to their age and the time that has elapsed since that experience.

CHAPTER 2

EXISTING RESEARCH AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

It is no secret that historically marginalized groups underperform on many measures when compared to their peers from dominant groups. Locally, this disparity is most glaring for our Latinx students, and more microscopically, for those Latinx students who are the first in their families to pursue post-secondary education here in the United States. This study aims to uncover teachers' tangible policies, practices, and attitudes that had the greatest impact on those students' academic success. Importantly, the intention is to empower those students' voices by asking them to share their actual lived experience in school, allowing them to name those impactful policies, practices and attitudes for themselves. At the beginning of this chapter, I review the robust epistemological foundation of this study. Next, I thoroughly review of the empirical research related to the dissertation topic. I conclude with a chapter summary.

Epistemological Foundation

The epistemological foundation for this study rests on the core tenets of critical race theory (CRT), relying predominantly on the work of Harris (1993) and Ladson-Billings (1998). Essential components of CRT include acknowledging that racism itself is a normal aspect of American society and arguing that Whites in fact are the main beneficiaries of policy even when it is couched as "civil rights" legislation (Ladson-Billings, 1998). While CRT transcends far beyond the classroom, the focus here will be the ways in which it directly impacts schools and schooling in the United States broadly, and specifically in the EWUSD, the initial focus of this study. Within that framework, aspects of Whiteness as Power, Whiteness as Privilege, and Whiteness as Property will be addressed.

Whiteness as Power

The power imbalance between White educators and the children of color they serve is manifested in policies, practices and expectations set by White adults for the non-White students in their care.

Gillborn (2007) argues that this inherently problematic power imbalance originates as Whiteness itself draws much of its power from “Othering” the very idea of ethnicity.

A component of CRT is the overt acknowledgement that there are direct, tangible benefits to racial, cultural, and physiological “Whiteness.” Some of these benefits are overt, but many are insidiously tacit. Of course, a critical investigation of Whiteness is not an attack on White people per se. Gillborn (2007) who is echoed by Leonardo (2002), cautions against viewing the conversation as a critique of White people (based on skin color), but rather of whiteness as a racial discourse. They both see critical scholarship on Whiteness as an intellectual attack on the “socially constructed and constantly reinforced power of white identifications and interests” (Gillborn, 2007 p. 488). One way in which this is done is by treating Whiteness as outside of identification with any racial group; in fact, specific examples highlight the ways in which White teachers individualize themselves (as outside of any cultural or ethnic “Whiteness” larger than the individual) while simultaneously grouping all students of other races and cultures into collectives (Vaught & Castagno, 2008).

Even well-meaning White “allies” tend to perpetuate the imbalance generated by Whiteness as power. Patton and Bondi (2015) explain that “White allies tend to direct others, take leadership and focus on self, rather than listening to and partnering with nondominant populations” (p. 490). While these allies may feel like they are “modeling” in good faith, CRT uncovers the subtle way in which even modeling—with the expectation that others will mimic the words, actions, and mindset being modeled—leads to an emphasis on “sameness.” Examples of this kind of “mainstreaming” of students of color can be seen in dress codes, uniform policies, reclassification criteria for emerging bilingual students, and other prerequisites for academic and extracurricular opportunities alike. This again privileges Whites as holders of the characteristics valued by the society they created (Ladson-Billings, 1998), which is exacerbated by the power dynamic inherent in the educator/student relationship. Howe (1997) calls this the “White standard of comparison,” noting it is troubling to require “disempowered groups to abide by rules they had no part in formulating and whose interests such rules do not serve” (p. 102). This is an

inherent perpetuation of power, which in some cultural and sociological settings would be considered a manifestation of “coercive isomorphism,” as White decision-makers make rules and expectations for non-White participants to follow and mirror (Beckert, 2010, p. 152).

Whiteness as Privilege

The process of creating and implementing policies intended to improve the status of minorities—broadly known as being an ally—has been discussed at length by Patton and Bondi (2015). They cite others who analyze the intersection of the rationale for what could be termed allyship (i.e.,: self-interest, altruism, or social justice) and identify the abilities automatically afforded White allies based on their privilege (i.e.,: paraphrase but get credit as if it was original, be emotional without being accused of being “too angry,” or earn praise for the same work that gets people of color vilified) (Edwards, 2006; Osayande, 2013). These converging, and sometimes competing, positionalities are reminiscent of Bell’s (1980) discussion around “interest convergence” (p. 523). He points to the landmark Supreme Court case, *Brown v Board of Education*, and argues that case would never have been decided in what looks to be in favor of minority students unless some aspect of passage was simultaneously beneficial to Whites as well; in this case, middle and upper-class Whites believed that nominal equality in education via desegregation and related measures may in fact “secure, advance, or at least not harm societal interests deemed important by middle and upper class whites” and that there would be potential “economic and political advances at home and abroad” (pp. 523-524). This challenge to the possible illusion of altruism mirrors later discourse that even White allies’ efforts to help can be problematic because they are couched in the White privilege of a deeply socialized expectation to be in control (Patton & Bondi, 2015).

In a very specific case study, Vaught and Castagno (2008) looked at large urban school districts and how they provided PD around culturally responsive teaching and “White privilege” to their predominantly White teacher staffs (p. 95). A common thread is the inability of White teachers to see themselves as contributing to the perpetuation of systemic and structural racism. Individual White

teachers use the argument, “I’m not like that” to deny *personal* privilege, which fails to acknowledge the systematic privilege conferred to all White people whether they chose it or not (Vaught & Castagno, 2008). They also discuss teachers’ reliance on “formal equality”—giving minorities the same *de facto* material access—and how such “bare opportunities” (Howe, 1997) fall short. Formal equality fails to address the structural and systemic struggles that minorities will face that the majority inherently does not. It is important to highlight how this is a structural problem; the amount of time a family spends in poverty—including generationally—the lower the likelihood they will meet certain social and academic milestones. This can be attributed to several factors, including residential instability and low levels of parental education (Ratcliffe, 2015). An example of what this might look like is a first-generation Latinx (FGL) student who is a junior in high school working 25 hours per week to help his family pay for food and rent; he inherently has fewer hours to devote to study than his White peer whose family can afford for him not to work. In other words, these two students have the same opportunity to *take* certain classes, but not the same opportunity to find success in them. Through this lens, White teachers were found to rationalize a belief in the meritocracy that led to their families’ historical success, while completely deflecting the role that structural racism plays in who is and is not finding similar success both historically and today (Vaught & Castagno, 2008).

Whiteness as Property

Others have also questioned the ability for White allies to act with a complete absence of self-interest because of the entrenched and deep-rooted privilege that itself bestows many of the tools that Whites use to advocate for others, including social predisposition to trusting and inherently valuing suggestions and ideas offered by Whites. Foundational work on the prevalence of these privileges is found in the seminal work by Harris (1993) around “Whiteness as Property.” She uncovers the simultaneously tangible and invisible privileges afforded by Whiteness (both as a social construct and as a literal skin color), and her framework is often used by others to evaluate existing work on equity, including through the lens of allyship (Patton & Bondi, 2015; Vaught & Castagno, 2008).

Harris' work is foundational to further scholarship around the insidious way that the construct of "Whiteness" benefits its possessors in ways both seen and unseen, often simultaneously tangible and nebulous at once. Aggarwal (2016) traces education policy and its intersection with the material benefits of Whiteness and the corresponding material harm—in the form of continuing inequality in educational outcomes—befallen upon non-White students.

Taken to its original sin, the root of Whiteness as property traces back to the scourge of the European conscription of Africans as slaves. Harris (1993) powerfully writes:

Slavery as a system of property facilitated the merger of white identity and property. Because the system of slavery was contingent on and conflated with racial identity, it became crucial to be 'white,' to be identified as white, to have the property of being white. Whiteness was the characteristic, the attribute, the property of free human beings. (p. 1721)

This conflation between skin tone and human worth has long perpetuated the power of both Whiteness and property ownership as giving some "the right to exclude" others (Harris, 1993, p. 1714). In fact, as seen through the experience of enslaved Africans and the outright theft of lands belonging to Natives of north America, "the origins of property rights in the United States are rooted in racial domination" (Harris, 1993, p. 1716). Within the realm of schools, this exclusion in practice looks like students of color being dissuaded to pursue certain opportunities, or nominally objective prerequisites that disproportionately benefit wealthier, often White, students.

If one questions the power of Whiteness and the impulse to assimilate, look no further than the many people of color who have attempted "passing" as White to acquire the benefits of Whiteness. This same assimilation is present in classrooms across the United States, as policy decisions ranging from curriculum choices, to dress codes, to discipline policies protect White norms and punish those who do not conform. As Harris (1993) describes, "the set of assumptions, privileges and benefits that accompany the status of being white" are so inherently valuable that Whites "have come to expect and rely on these benefits, and over time these expectations have been affirmed, legitimated, and protected by the law" (p. 1713). She concludes with a reminder of how asymmetrical the power relationship

between Whites and people of color is, as Whiteness—that which is valuable and is characteristically synonymous with property—became embedded in the definition of what is worthwhile and is something “which Whites alone possess” (Harris, 1993, p. 1721).

Review of the Scholarly Empirical Literature

The existing research around FGL students can help create a thorough picture of who they are, what many of their lived experiences are, what makes their educational journey more difficult, and what is already being done to address some of those challenges. While not a monolith by any means, this section will describe commonly observed characteristics of FGL students. Next, this section will review the typical manifestations of explicit bias placed upon FGL students by teachers in the school setting. Following that is an explanation of typically observed disparities in outcomes for FGL students, concluding with discussion around the broad impacts of CRP on FGL students in public schools.

Characteristics of First-Generation Latinx Students

The research describing FGL students is broad and relevant to this study. In this section, I focus my review of research on addressing typical characteristics of FGL students in terms of generalizable personal and sociological attributes.

Attributes

The research surrounding FGL students provides several common characteristics that often apply to this group. Importantly, Latinx students are not monolithic; the term represents students from several different countries of origin, including Guatemala, El Salvador, Puerto Rico and Cuba to name a few. In general, however, Latinx students attending post-secondary schooling are overwhelmingly representative of Mexican heritage in the United States—64%—according to research from the Pew Research Center (2016).

It is important to determine the definition of “first-generation” in the context of this study. While a common definition is often described as a student being the first in their family to attend college, a more recent definition that is quite broadly accepted is defined as a student whose parents have not

finished or completed a college degree (in the United States, for the purposes of this study) (Petty, 2014; Toutkoushian et al., 2015).

Another common experience of FGL students is their position in the socio-economic sphere. Often, FGL students come from families who experience financial struggles and are of low socio-economic status (SES) (Horn & Nunez, 2000; Hernandez & Lopez, 2005). This is not always the case, but it is quite common and often leads to students needing to work to help pay bills and support the cost of family expenses, particularly for high school aged FGL males (O’Neal et al., 2016; Martinez et al., 2009). This prioritization of commitment to family is also a frequently observed characteristic of FGL students, and is manifested in part time work, childcare, and volunteering to support a parent’s employment (Bernal & Domenech Rodriguez, 2009; Nunez et al., 2013). This commitment to family has been described as “the guilt of success” sometimes felt especially by eldest siblings who feel like they are “abandoning” their family by pursuing education in lieu of full-time employment. This is further exacerbated when pursuit of post-secondary education involves leaving the home (Moreno, 2021).

These characteristics not only impact the typical course of study chosen by an FGL student, but they replicate it and perpetuate it as well. In part due to the commitments and obligations FGL students make to supporting their family financially, they are disproportionately unlikely to take a college preparatory course of study (Choy, 2001). In addition, studies indicate that the older siblings act as models for the younger siblings, who often follow a similar trajectory of working to support the family and avoiding a college preparatory course of study (Delgado, 2020).

Another commonly shared characteristic of FGL students is their status as participants in a language minority. They typically speak a language other than English in the home as their first language—and it is often the only language spoken by their parents. This designates them as emerging bilingual students (English language learners in current educational vernacular) who must prove themselves as proficient in English prior to accessing the same extracurricular opportunities as their English-only peers (Niehaus & Kumpiene, 2014).

Importantly, there are many cases of Latinx students finding success academically and achieving more equitable outcomes. Some argue that their success may be a direct result of conscious institutional mechanisms but nonetheless contend that Latinx students can find success (Conchas, 2001). Others contend that such institutional mechanisms, when based in CRT policy and practice, can positively influence the educational progress and academic attainment of Latinx students (Sólorzano et al., 2005). Another component of Latinx students who are finding academic success is coming in the form of pride in their cultural roots and unapologetic appreciation for the stories of their families; these students leverage their pride to believe that any future is attainable for them if they work hard for it (Feliciano, 2000). Other supports that specifically assist Latinx students in their pursuit of positive educational outcomes, including for those who may be undocumented, exist in the form of policies such as Assembly Bill 540; such structural and policy supports have been shown to contribute to increased access to higher education for Latinx students regardless of their immigration status (Chavez et al., 2007).

Teachers' Implicit Bias

A significant body of research has addressed the impact of implicit bias. In this section, I review research surrounding implicit bias as a concept broadly, followed by a closer look at research addressing implicit bias towards Latinx students specifically, which I will attempt to frame in terms of how it is manifested by White teachers.

The Broader Concept

The research addressing bias as a general concept appears frequently in the arenas of psychology and sociology. Implicit bias more specifically is categorized as something that is unconsciously activated and measured most often by clocking response times to certain prompts that elicit assumptions. These assumptions can automatically influence a person's judgement via generalization based on assumptions about a whole group (Banaji & Hardin, 1996). Not only do implicit biases influence

judgment about character, but they also have the potential to skew the literal perception of the viewer regardless of his or her level of explicit prejudice (Payne, 2001).

Another component of implicit bias is that it can exist and persist despite “conscious nonprejudiced attitudes or intentions,” causing people to perpetuate discrimination via unwitting complicity (Devine et al., 2012, p. 1267). In addition to the lack of awareness making implicit bias difficult to identify, it has been shown to be a powerful determinant of behavior in ways that can have tangible impacts on others. Dovidio and Gaertner (2000) found that implicit bias leads to real-world discrimination in many areas, as wide-ranging as job prospects, salary levels, and even the basic daily interactions with social superiors.

Some research frames bias in terms of “warmth” versus “competence,” which can have an outsized impact on perceptions of first-generation students, including different perceptions for different groups. Fiske et al. (2002) describe the way that paternalistic attitudes of teachers towards those students “outside” of the dominant in-group assume a lack of competence and enable a lowering of expectations. Next is a closer look at these concepts vis-à-vis FGL students.

Latinx Students

Many studies have shed light on the ways in which implicit bias generally has damaging implications more specifically for certain groups. In education, there are several aspects that directly impact perceptions and treatment of Latinx students. Within Fiske’s matrix of warmth and competence, Latinx students were found to be viewed predominantly as possessing “warm” characteristics (friendliness, disadvantaged, deserving of help) and lacking in “competence,” due to factors such as an accent when speaking English and a belief that they belong to a group that has not historically been perceived as socioeconomically successful. These perceptions also correlate with expectations, with students from ethnic minorities having increased susceptibility to negative teacher expectations (Lee & Fiske, 2006; van den Bergh et al., 2010). This view is further exacerbated in perceptions of males versus females as well, with the risk of intersectional invisibility that can occur when negative stereotypes of

multiple groups overlap—a non-White female, for example—and can conversely mitigate the impacts of bias when positive stereotypes of one group compensate for the negative stereotypes of another—being non-White (negative bias) but also being male (positive assumptions) (Cole, 2009; Kang & Bodenhausen, 2015).

Another way that biases negatively impact Latinx students are in the ways that White teachers expect them to behave. Research indicates that those students are often viewed as behaviorally problematic prior to any interactions, and that teachers operate in such a way as to perpetuate the social reproduction of expected behaviors according to norms established by the dominant group. This manifests both through self-fulfilling prophecies (teachers are looking for misbehavior so they find it) and self-maintaining expectations (teachers set a lower expectation and the Pygmalion Effect—a psychological phenomenon in education where students meet the expectations of their teachers, either high or low—takes place). Cultural differences also impact how White teachers view non-White students' self-expression both verbally and non-verbally, such as reading negativity into body-language when it may often be innocuous (Collins, 2009; van den Bergh et al., 2010).

Additionally, whether overt or otherwise, discrimination and exclusion become part of the Latinx student's experience in public school. Dovidio et al. (2010) describe ways in which discrimination occurs in response to students' accents as well as the perception that they are culturally different than the normative 'White American.' They also note that exclusion stems from perceptions of immigration status, with association to "illegal status" being common regardless of actual citizenship.

Disparities in Outcomes

In addition to the biases present amongst educators and the systems of education themselves, many empirical studies have examined the resulting disparities in educational outcomes for FGL students. I focus the review here on disparities that are related to both academics as well as discipline.

Academics

The research addressing FGL students highlights disparities in outcomes along a broad range of measures, including graduation rates and participation in post-secondary educational opportunities. These disparities are linked to discrimination (including stigmas and stereotypes), as well as a lack of access to a culturally relevant course of study. At the outset, it is important to be clear about the abundance of scholarship that reinforces the fact that Latinx students indeed face an achievement gap that grows over the time they spend in public school (Benner & Graham, 2011; Farkas, 2003; Gándara & Contreras, 2009)

Discrimination in the form of differential treatment of and expectations for Latinx students is shown to negatively impact both academic performance and attendance rates. Both factors contribute to lower high school graduation rates and post-secondary attendance (Saenz et al., 2007). Researchers find a recursive relationship between experiences of discrimination and differential treatment, and high rates of absenteeism, which is itself correlated with worse academic performance. In this way, the school culture of exclusion and discrimination leads to both poor attendance and lower grades (Benner & Graham, 2011).

Another negative impact on FGL students' academic outcomes has been found because of self-fulfilling prophecies and stigma consciousness. Guyll et al. (2010) found that educational outcome disparities begin as early as preschool and can be found at "all subsequent markers of achievement" including traditional compulsory schooling and post-secondary schooling as well (p. 113). They note that teachers' treatment of Latinx students is negatively impacted by stereotypical judgments and expectations, again deteriorating the school culture experienced by Latinx students and the corresponding deterioration of academic outcomes (Guyll et al., 2010).

Discipline

In addition to negative academic outcomes, many studies have found measurable impacts on FGL students in the realm of school discipline. Their disproportionate experiences include the frequency

and intensity of punishment, as well as how teachers perceive them vis-à-vis compliant behavior. Researchers have also examined the degree to which Latinx students become excluded from the classroom as a function of school discipline. One way in which Latinx students face discrimination is in the disproportionate experience of school discipline. Latinx students encounter a tangible disciplinary measure—such as school suspension—at proportional rates higher than their representation in the student body (Benner & Graham, 2011). The reality of disproportionate punishment for Latinx students is corroborated by others as well in studies of Latinx students in schools across the United States (Peguero & Shekarkhar, 2011; Skiba et al., 2011).

Not only do students experience discriminatory discipline, but their perception of school fairness indicates that schools and teachers cause them to feel unfairly treated as well (Benner & Graham, 2011; Cortesão, 2011). This is also highlighted by Cortesão (2011) in a study about teacher perceptions of noncompliance; when interacting with students outside the dominant culture, teachers saw behavior as “indiscipline” and desired stronger compliance (p. 266). Further scholarship on teacher perception also indicate that non-Latinx teachers tend to gauge Latinx students as threatening, and the degree to which they perceive that threat correlates to the severity of punitive responses on those students (Welch & Payne, 2018).

Lastly, the type of discipline that Latinx students experience has been described as problematic as well. Versions of suspension—ranging from brief removal from a classroom, suspension from certain classes, in-home suspension for a period, or removal of access to extracurricular privileges—are considered “exclusionary” and permeate many Latinx students’ experience (Anyon et al., 2018). Importantly, Anyon et al. (2018) showed that Latinx students were no more likely to have incidents meriting exclusionary discipline (ie: suspension) in unstructured settings such as bathrooms and hallways yet still received a disproportionate amount of disciplinary actions categorized as exclusionary.

Culturally Relevant Pedagogy

The research around existing responses to FGL student needs, including causes (such as implicit bias) and results (such as disparate outcomes) of their lived experience, includes CRP. I examine research around the concept and its existing impact on FGL students.

Impact of CRP

Research surrounding CRP describes the ways in which it manifests in schools as well as individual classrooms. It also examined the impacts that its presence (and absence) can have on students from outside the mainstream culture. I will review research surrounding pedagogy, social-emotional learning (SEL), student perceptions of caring, and the potential influence of teachers who reflect minority students.

One aspect of CRP is its nature as a response to an increasingly diverse student body. Cortesão (2011) argued that pedagogically speaking, schools have long perpetuated the status quo in support of maintaining the dominant culture. Whether manifested in discipline policy, or in the constant recycling of practices and lessons year over year—a phenomenon known as “resting routines”—teachers both consciously and subconsciously reward students for compliance and conformity (Cortesão, 2011, p. 265). Other research also describes such a “pedagogy of poverty,” which relies on direct instruction and punishment of noncompliance at its core. This teacher practice, too, perpetuates low expectations for students outside of the mainstream and fails to deliver equitably complex learning for those students (Haberman, 1991, p. 291).

Another component of CRP is the intersection with focus on student well-being. While applicable to all students, those outside of the mainstream can benefit from intentional work by teachers and schools around SEL. Yoshikawa et al. (2012) highlighted the effects of poverty on children’s health (mental, emotional, and behavioral), including “delays to language and cognitive development” as well as “academic achievement and educational attainment” (p. 273). One mitigating practice can be found in intentional mediating interventions that are specifically targeted to support families experiencing

poverty, and that in concert with multiple culturally relevant and appropriate responses (parent education and support, classroom interventions), student outcomes can be improved (Yoshikawa et al., 2012).

In addition to highlighting challenges for students outside the dominant culture, CRP also provides additional potential amelioration to how those students feel about school and schooling. Focusing on Latinx students in particular, studies indicate that they thrive when they feel genuinely cared for and engaged in authentic learning (Garza, 2009; Perez, 2000). More specifically, Garza (2009) found that Latinx students desired teachers who they perceived as “always available,” and especially those who showed a personal interest in their well-being beyond the walls of the classroom (p. 310). Teachers’ establishment of an emotional connection and students’ perceptions of being cared for are recurring themes in terms of ways in which CRP can improve academic outcomes for FGL students (López, 2016; Perez, 2000). This is even more specifically seen in studies when teachers view access to the Spanish language as an asset and when they express cultural knowledge and appreciation for the Latinx culture more broadly (López, 2016).

Lastly, some research also looked at the impact of having teachers who may not reflect the students that they teach. Kohli and Pizarro (2016) examined the experience from the perspective of teachers of color and how their efforts to provide CRP to schools and classrooms clash with existing hierarchies of both ontology and epistemology, making it exhausting for them to advance justice on behalf of the students they serve. Their research also implied an inherent divide between White teachers and the students of color in their classrooms, as the hegemony of individualism tends to overshadow and diminish the space for communities of color which tend to be community-oriented; more research is needed regarding the degree to which those students perceive that gap themselves (Kohli & Pizarro, 2016).

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is grounded in the interplay between how Whiteness (as power, privilege, and property) can negatively impact the educational experience of FGL students, and

the ways in which CRP can ameliorate and reduce those negative impacts. The ways in which Latinx students are viewed by teachers, and how teachers' implicit biases can exacerbate disparities in outcomes, are framed within the tension between the competing impacts of Whiteness and CRP.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework for Empirical Literature Review

CHAPTER 3

METHOD OF INQUIRY

Taking voluminous academic achievement data from a diverse school district, and the disparate outcomes for students from persistently marginalized groups are frustratingly predictable. One can guess with painfully accurate precision the demographic or socioeconomic background of students based on the achievement data. In the EWUSD, this scenario plays out predictably across and between the vastly different schools and their literally segregated student populations. Both historical and concurrent data tell us that specific student groups—most prominently low-income and Latinx students in this district specifically—will underperform their traditionally more privileged peers in measures of academic success (publicly available School Accountability Report Card—SARC—data shows this). This affront to equity and justice must be addressed, and understanding the factors that can counteract such disproportionate outcomes can and should come from the voices and perspectives of marginalized students themselves.

The purpose of this study was to discover whether there are tangible and concrete components of K-12 education—both in the character of educators as practitioners and the practices inherent in education as a system—that lead to, facilitate, and catalyze increased academic achievement for persistently underserved student populations, as defined by the FGL student population in their own words. In pursuit of this knowledge, it is important to look carefully at the following questions:

1. What personal qualities or characteristics do FGL students value most in their White teachers?
2. What classroom policies or practices do FGL students find beneficial when implemented by White teachers?

In this chapter, I first present the role of the researcher and their positionality. Next, I provide a description of the research design within my selected methodological approach that I used in this study, starting with a discussion of its philosophical foundations. Following the research design, I detailed the specific research methods used in this study. This description includes information about the setting,

sample, data collection including instrumentation and procedure, and data analysis including validity/trustworthiness. I conclude with a chapter summary.

Researcher Role and Positionality

I did not set out to write a dissertation regarding a topic about which I feel “neutral.” For better or worse, I am feverishly passionate about the opportunities and outcomes for FGL students. I care deeply about doing work that catalyzes more equitable results for students I have long seen as extra-deserving and under-served. My own career arc is steeped in this work. For my first teaching job, I was hired to teach multiple levels of English language development at a majority-Latinx, Title 1 eligible (though not declared) high school. From there, I was tapped to become an AVID teacher (despite not having any idea what the program was or what it did). I remained an English language development teacher for the entirety of my 12-year teaching career, and I was both an AVID teacher and coordinator for 11 of those 12 years. Even now as a principal, I chose to work at a Title 1 middle school, comprised of 98% Latinx students and 97% low-income, and then I accepted appointment as principal to a Title 1 elementary school with similar demographics. Everything I did as a teacher and do as a school administrator revolves around working with predominantly Latinx students, an overwhelming majority of whom are the first generation in their families to pursue post-secondary education in the United States.

Because of my proximity to this topic and this work—not to mention to some of the subjects of the research themselves—I needed to be extremely mindful about my positionality on the participant-observer continuum. Indeed, one of my primary modes of securing research subjects was to rely first on former students of mine who met the criteria for this study. Their accessibility to me made them ideal candidates, but their personal connection to me and my work as an educator made intentionality around checking my biases and depersonalizing my interpretation of their responses paramount.

One major pitfall to avoid is related to my interpretation of the qualitative data provided through the interview process. Because some of the participants are former students of mine, I needed to ensure

that I was not looking for positive reinforcement or validation of my own work or of my own qualities in their responses. I also needed to actively work to establish the researcher role vis-à-vis my former students qua students. It was important to avoid influencing their responses—inadvertently or otherwise—by reinforcing that our conversation was not intended to be in the realm of “teacher/student” but rather of “observer/participant.” This was easier said than done but was worth the effort in order to promote the generation of meaningful and reasonably objective qualitative data.

In terms of what can be called “Subjective I’s” (Peshkin, 1988), my “subjectivity audit” has uncovered what I referred to as my “White Savior I” (p. 18). I have found that there is some degree of White guilt that permeates my psyche. I want nothing more than to right the wrongs of history and find great gratification in doing work that elevates and supports historically marginalized people. Upon reflection, I find that I feel some sort of obligation to do such work, and I needed to keep awareness of this fact at a highly conscious level during my research. I did not want to have an image of what answers I already *wanted* them to give, because it would have been too easy to hear what I wanted to hear.

Another “Subjective I” about which I needed to remain vigilant is what I would call my “Honorary Latinx I” (p. 18). Because I have spent nearly half of my life serving almost exclusively Latinx students, I have become familiar with and enamored by many aspects of Latinx culture (predominantly Mexican), which has caused some allies to bestow me with a title of “honorary Latino.” Despite never taking a class or formally studying, I have become conversationally fluent in Spanish; I can argue about the Chivas versus Club America rivalry; I honor the nuances of Mexican Mother’s Day and the Posada; I attended quinceñeras and bite the cake on my birthday. And as proud as I am of my learning around a culture different from my own, I am *not* Mexican, nor Latinx, and my lived experience is fundamentally different from those who are. I have not known the marginalization and its insidious effects like my former students and other participants have and continue to feel.

To temper the inherent subjectivities that I bring to the research, I utilized a coding system that removed emotion and opinion to the degree possible. I also worked to calibrate my coding system with

at least one other outside observer who could view the transcripts dispassionately and without predetermination. This was designed to add validity to my analysis and conclusions; inter-coder reliability was essential and only themes and codes that were consistent at 80% similarity with the outside coder were included as reliable conclusions.

Finally, I needed to acknowledge my own predeterminations in terms of what I expected to hear from my participants. Because of my extensive experience with these students, I had several ideas about what findings I expected to discover. If I was not careful, I would miss or omit new data that did not comport with that which I already expected to find. This did not mean I could not include some findings that were legitimately from the participants, and which also matched prior expectations. But, I needed to ensure that I was hearing, noticing, recording, and reporting whatever it was that my subjects provided, even if it contradicted my underlying assumptions.

Research Design

This is ultimately a study about people; it is about a specific group of people and their real lived experiences. To illuminate their stories in a way that is robust, authentic, and reactive, I performed a qualitative study rooted in personal, one-on-one conversations within a semi-structured format. The epistemological underpinnings for why a qualitative study was most appropriate to answer these research questions is supported by multiple scholars. First, qualitative research is responsive to the human nature of change, and the nature of interactivity is inherent in this format (Corbin & Strauss, 1990). Also, it allows for—requires, really—intentional steps to provide validity, reliability, and credibility; these steps support to the plausibility and adequacy of the research.

Miles et al. (2014) described qualitative research as reactive and adaptive, and they note that it involved an ongoing dialogue between ideas and collected data. In terms of the importance to this study, qualitative design emphasizes people's lived experiences and, as a research method, is more capable of "revealing complexity" (Miles et al., 2014, p. 220). This method was most appropriate for this study because its focused on people, its emphasis on descriptions rather than raw numbers, and its orientation

towards making meaning (Maxwell, 2013). This study resembles what was described by Creswell and Guetterman (2021) as a “narrative research design” (p. 69).

An essential goal of this study is to empower the lives and voices of the actual students who have experienced and been impacted by the traditional schooling afforded them within the EWUSD, Grove High School (GHS) (pseudonym), and beyond. In pursuit of this goal, narrative research allowed those individuals to tell their stories; this researcher is committed to magnifying the voices of the researched.

To uncover (and illuminate) their voices, sessions modeled from “empathy interviews” (The Holdsworth Center, 2020) were used. Use of a highly structured inquiry paradigm was combined with more open-ended dialogue when and where appropriate or called for. A key component of the empathy interview process involved gaining the confidence of interviewees, which is why the first several minutes of each interview involved a consistent script designed to create comfort and trust, as well as share personal details designed to build a sense of openness and two-way communication (Rubin & Rubin, 2012).

Research Methods

In this section, I will describe the specific research methods that I utilized in what is most accurately referred to as “narrative research design” (Creswell & Guetterman, 2021). I will discuss the setting, sample, data collection, data analysis, and steps taken to ensure validity or trustworthiness.

Setting

The setting for this study was some parts geographic and some parts chronological. In terms of geography, all initial (“known”) participants lived in the attendance area of GHS at least during the time that they attended and graduated from secondary school. This includes the many pockets of high-density housing to the south of as well as directly adjacent to the school. The “snowball” (unknown) participants varied in terms of geography, but they attended at least some K-12 schooling in Southern California. In terms of time chronology, all participants graduated from high school between the years of 2010 and 2020. While still broad, this narrows the initial participant pool considerably given that the school has

had over 80 graduating classes in its history, and the extension of recommended participants came solely from known participants, narrowing the sample size.

While the EWUSD is quite diverse as an entire district, the setting applicable to this study in terms of initial known participants was centered around specific regions that place students on the feeder pattern for elementary and middle schools that ultimately lead to attendance at GHS. This encompasses portions of three different suburban cities in southern California, each of which contains pockets of high-density housing populated predominantly by Latinx families.

While this research context is arguably broad, it was appropriate and necessary for this study. To draw themes out of participants' words, it was useful to find common experiences shared by FGL students at the same school over many years. This was done in the hope that embedded institutional concerns might be illuminated, or progression (or regression) might also have become apparent. Focusing on graduates from similar demographic backgrounds but across time had the potential to help see which longitudinal patterns, if any, exist or persist.

The voices of FGL students were necessary here because they highlighted the lived experience of historically marginalized people in their own words. This is also not only appropriate, but valuable in this context, juxtaposed with the impact of the social reproduction theory in these communities (James & Amato, 2013). The belief was that much could be gained from discovering components of the school context that helped students avoid the social reproduction often present in their neighborhoods.

Sample

The initial participant pool for this study included graduates of the EWUSD who attended GHS specifically, and it focused on FGL students. In this context, first-generation refers to students whose parents or guardians did not attend post-secondary schooling in the United States. Also in this context, Latinx refers to students from any predominantly Spanish-speaking country in north or central America (including, but not limited to, Mexico, Guatemala, El Salvador, and Honduras).

These graduates in the initial participant pool ranged in age from 18-year-old recent graduates to interviewees in their 30s from my first years as a teacher. It was purposeful sampling in terms of focusing first on graduates from a particular feeder pattern, and it covered a span of years which facilitated generalizing the findings to those that were less likely to be unique to a particular cohort. The goal was to pursue a balance in the gender distribution of participants, and I initially thought there would be more female participants based on my initial pool consisting of former students; as an AVID teacher, I regularly experienced a much higher proportion of female students to male in the AVID elective. I started accessing participants by reaching out to former students with whom I still had contact. Many of them were personal contacts whom I called or texted anytime, while others were merely acquaintances on social media.

In addition to using some former students as participants, I had them refer me to their peers who did not have me as a teacher. Known as “snowball sampling,” this was especially important in my effort to diversify the perspectives I had access to, and to reduce the bias that I brought to my listening and interpretation of interviews with graduates that I knew or had known for many years.

While a large pool is preferable, I was comfortable with a participant pool that meets the minimum threshold for producing reliable and valid data in a qualitative study that relies on narrative research. Ultimately, I intended to interview at least 8-10 graduates spanning multiple graduating classes and ended up interviewing a total of 12 participants. Also, to reiterate, it was essential to obtain data from participants who met the criteria but who were never my students. In addition to this distinction, I also hoped to interview some FGL students who participated in the AVID program in high school and some who did not, which I was able to do.

The participants have lived through the research problem and were the best candidates for responding to questions about it. So often, well-meaning educators—me included—performed what they perceived to be the “right work” in terms of providing a just, equitable, and inclusive education for as many students as possible. But we often fail to solicit feedback about the impact of our efforts from

those who experience it with the most proximity: our students in their own voices. To explore what demeanors, attitudes, policies and practices catalyze successful attitudes for FGL students in the EWUSD and beyond, we must empower the voices of those who can best respond because they literally lived it.

The initial selection of participants was partially based on the practical ease of contemporary access to them. This list started with students from the classes of 2010-2015 that I still communicate with and for whom I have personal contact information. This period also represented students I taught for both 11th and 12th grade, providing a strong foundation for trust and willingness to contribute to something important to me such as this dissertation. Branching off from this initial list, I asked each of the participants that I have known from their time in my classroom to invite at least one of their peers who was not ever in my class to participate as well (this included peers they met in college or in the workplace, as long as they meet the chronological graduation and FGL criteria). This was intended to ensure that I did not gather data solely from participants who might have subjective biases that would skew both my gathering and interpretation of their responses. The demographics of these students fell within the focus of the study, limited to FGL students. As hoped for, there was a mix of male and female participants; though I anticipated higher proportion of female subjects, the final cohort had more males.

To ensure anonymity and protect the identity of respondents, I used pseudonyms for everyone. This was in addition to the pseudonyms being used for both the district broadly and the school site specifically. Such anonymity was essential as a buffer that enabled participants to share freely without fear of retribution or retaliation. This was important because the community represented in this study was tight-knit and generational. Teachers at the schools they discussed have been there for many years and some were still teaching there, and these participants may have siblings or other family members in classrooms currently led by teachers described in their responses to these research questions; ensuring these participants could speak freely without fear of repercussions for anyone close to or literally related

to them was paramount. All of these precautions were explained in the Participant Consent Form (Appendix B).

Data Collection and Management

Qualitative data, while often perceived as less “concrete” or objective as quantitative measures, must still be produced, collected, managed and organized in a methodical and thorough manner.

Following are my processes for instrumentation, data collection, and data management.

Instrumentation

The predominant form of instrumentation for this study was an interview protocol that I created. It was designed to elicit information from subjects in a safe, empathetic environment and manner. After practicing with empathy interviews during my coursework, I modeled my interview protocol for data gathering after the experiences I had when implementing empathy interviews. In addition to modeling it from that experience, I also went through the process of practicing the protocol with subjects who would meet the criteria for my research study. The revision process was iterative, as I reflected on and modified the protocol after each practice session.

For the initial creation of the interview protocol, I relied on the suggestions and examples found in Rubin and Rubin (2012). This included important procedures that facilitated building rapport with the participant and encouraged a progressive structure to the questions and their order. I was particularly mindful about building towards questions that might be more difficult to answer, whether for their complexity or for their potential emotional resonance for the subjects.

To pursue rich data from interviewees, I utilized a format consisting of main questions, punctuated by follow-up and probe questions when possible (Rubin & Rubin, 2012). I was also very intentional around the degree to which my questions were open-ended. By avoiding questions that could be answered with “yes” or “no,” I attempted to force the subjects to elaborate on topics; I also tried to provide space for nuance and nebulosity. By creating a protocol with no “right” or “wrong” answers,

my participants were given ample space to explore their memories, thoughts and opinions based on my questions.

In terms of the process of modifying the interview protocol, I first practiced the protocol with participants who matched the profile sought for my study prior to beginning the actual research. After reflecting on the process and the data that came from it, I was able to change not only the content, but also the order of some of the questions from my original protocol. Specifically, after practice, I found that leading with questions about their positive experiences first was most effective in maintaining the comfort and trust of the researcher/participant relationship. Also, changing some of the language in the follow-up questions helped generate a more natural flow to the dialogue as well. This helped maximize the time spent building rapport early in the interview process, and it also provided more opportunities for deep reflection and thoughtful conversation, since the questions built steadily to a crescendo in terms of depth and complexity.

My deepest intention was to let the subjects and their voices take the research where they wanted to go, particularly when their responses lead to additional lines of inquiry not originally planned for in my initial vision; empowering their voices was paramount. An aim of this research was to do the work of sense-making, discovery of meaning, and highlighting potential “turning-point” experiences that guided students’ perceptions of their school experiences which informed this study and its potential impact on readers now and in the future (Drake, 2006).

Procedures

My procedure for data collection in this study was to participate in 12 semi-structured interviews with participants who matched the qualifying criteria based on my research goals. I met with them virtually and I utilized the functions made available through the Zoom application to help with automatic transcription and video recording. The camera captured and recorded their faces to provide added context that the transcriptions might not provide.

These interviews occurred over the span of two years after all necessary permissions and school board reviews were completed and I was officially given permission to conduct the interviews. The interviews lasted between 30-45 minutes each and utilized a combination of structure (specific interview protocol, see Appendix A) as well as semi-structured conversation that came up in real time during the interview. Participants were told unequivocally that they had the right to refuse to answer any question if they desired.

I gathered hand-written notes that I jotted down while having the conversation, as well as the transcripts of the video recording and written transcript that Zoom provided. The intention was to start the data analysis in the immediate aftermath of access to notes and transcripts, using real-time memos during and immediately after interviews, a technique recommended by Maxwell (2013). Next, I worked on coding for common themes to organize the information into descriptive, substantive categories (Maxwell, 2013). This was done prior to determining where the connections and meaning exist.

In terms of establishing inter-coder reliability, I shared 25% of the transcripts with an objective reader and asked them to code for main ideas and themes based on their perception. I compared their findings with my own and looked for overlap of similar themes to ensure that what I saw is what an outside viewer saw without context as well. Any major discrepancies were discussed and re-evaluated, and consistency at the 80% threshold was determined to be accepted as valid and reliable and included in the conclusions and analysis.

Data Management

Using my password protected device, I stored all original files (written, audio, and movie) in a folder labeled with an alphanumeric system that protected the identities of all participants to any outside observer. I additionally created a key for myself to keep track of the pseudonyms so I could always distinguish whose story I was representing at any moment in my reporting and analysis.

In addition to the systematically maintained folders for all original files on my password protected device, I also used my password protected device to code the transcripts of every interview. I

maintained the naming conventions that secured confidentiality of the coded transcripts as well.

Analysis was catalyzed by the coding process I used to label words and passages from participants that showed thematic patterns. Password protection and the use of pseudonyms were important layers of protection for the anonymity of my participants.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

This section will be organized by research the questions, including the data that was collected followed by the treatment and analysis of the collected data to answer the research questions. As part of the collection and interpretation process, recording and transcripts were coded for themes which were shared back with the participants to ensure that their voices were accurately being reflected, a process Rubin and Rubin (2012) termed “member checks” (p. xv). I am hyper-aware of my positionality in this research on multiple levels, including my existence in multiple privileged classes (cisgender, White, male, school administrator, etc.). I intended to avoid the “White savior” trap (Straubhaar, 2016) by magnifying and amplifying the words and experiences of the participants in ways that they themselves attested are accurate representations of their ideas, feelings, beliefs, and lived experiences.

I used a gerund-stem system to take raw data from multiple interviews and turn it into thematic data from which I generated conclusions about the beliefs and values of my study’s participants. I first reviewed transcriptions of my interviews and highlighted key words and phrases that provided insight into my research questions. Preliminary data analysis consisted of highlighting phrases or sections that fit into thematic categories. These categories were created as I reviewed the first few interviews and started to identify patterns. Once those patterns were discovered, I used a coding system to identify them, and then proceeded to code for those themes with each interview transcript.

Specifically, I used process coding in alignment with the intention behind each research question. For example, when coding in search of themes related to the first research question, I coded for adjectives that participants used to describe the teachers who made a positive impact on them. When

coding for themes related to the second research question, I coded for progressive verbs and gerunds that participants used to describe the actions of the teachers who made them feel welcomed and successful.

Once I generated codes and assigned them to each of the transcripts, I identified emergent themes, as well as any intersectionality that emerged from cross analysis between transcripts. I anticipated that some themes would align with both existing research and my lived experience as a teacher of these students; an emphasis on the power of relationships was something I expected to hear, as well as the empowering nature of an asset-based approach that authentically validated aspects of the Latinx students' culture. The complete process is exemplified in Table 1.

Table 1. Method of Inquiry

Research Question	Data to Collect	Analytical Approach
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What personal qualities or characteristics do first-generation Latinx students value most in their White teachers? • What classroom policies or practices do first-generation Latinx students find beneficial when implemented by White teachers? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General information about participants • Interview transcripts • Interview notes • Follow-up interviews when appropriate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Code transcripts for main ideas, common themes • Cultivate patterns • Collaborate with inter-coder • Member check • Formulate analysis

Ultimately, the potential for my own interpretation was a dangerous prospect at this juncture of the study, therefore it was essential to utilize an alternate coder to provide another perspective on what is being said by those who are participating in the study, which I will now address in terms of trustworthiness in data interpretation.

Validity and/or Trustworthiness

For this qualitative study, it is important to provide evidence that the data produced was trustworthy. One way to increase confidence in trustworthiness was to regularly perform member checks with the participants after our interview was finished. I shared the video and the transcript with them so

that they could effectively attest to the accuracy of recorded information. In addition to allowing the speakers themselves to have a say in the accuracy of my data, I also solicited an inter-rater to help provide added objectivity in terms of interpreting what was being said by participants. A high level of inter-rater reliability (at least 80%) helped ensure that my interpretations were not being completely skewed by my positionality vis-à-vis my participants, and provided increased confidence that the themes being expressed were genuinely meant by the words shared by the subjects. My process with my inter-rater involved sharing blank copies of transcripts that he coded separately. We calibrated 25% of the total transcripts with an ALPHA of .82 (calculated from 66 codes across all transcripts). Ultimately, any codes or themes that were found to be different were discussed and resolved by coming to consensus regarding what was or was not coded prior to final conclusions and analysis.

CHAPTER 4

FINDINGS

The purpose of this qualitative study was to analyze which personal qualities and characteristics, as well as classroom policies and practices, were possessed and implemented by White teachers that made a positive impact on the educational experiences and outcomes of FGL students. This will help site principals across California (and perhaps beyond) to select teachers—through the hiring process or the transfer portal—with the temperament and instructional ideology that best meet the needs of an increasingly diverse student population at all grade spans. More specifically, they can use these findings to look for impactful teachers in predominantly White candidate pools who will be serving predominantly Latinx student populations, based on the preferences and experiences of students from that background. This study addressed the following research questions:

1. What personal qualities or characteristics do FGL students value most in their White teachers?
2. What classroom policies or practices do FGL students find beneficial when implemented by White teachers?

I began Chapter 4 with findings applicable to the first research question regarding qualities and characteristics. I followed with findings that applied to the second research question regarding classroom policies and practices. This included both significant findings and unanticipated results, and leveraged portions of interviews in order to amplify participants' voices. All findings were disaggregated in multiple ways, including: the “in” group (students I had a previous relationship with), the “out” group (students connected to me by snowball sampling), and by biological sex (male or female). I concluded with a summary of my findings.

Characteristics of Findings

The overall findings were analyzed along the following criteria: there were 12 total participants. Out of that total, seven participants were people known to the researcher as they had been students of his sometime within the window used to determine the participant pool (high school graduating classes

between 2010 and 2020). The other five participants were unknown to the researcher and were acquired using snowball sampling; their contact information was shared with me by known participants and he reached out to them to request interviews. The overall breakdown, then, between the previously known (hereafter referred to as the “in” group) and previously unknown (hereafter referred to as the “out” group) was divided nearly in half. The seven “in” participants represented 58.3% of all members, while the “out” participants represented 41.7%.

Another general characteristic of the findings was the frequency of responses analyzed along the lines of biological sex. All participants identified as either biologically male or female, with the overall breakdown of the entire cohort including seven males (58.3% of participants) and five females (41.7% of participants). In relation to the sampling, the “in” group was comprised of four males (57.1% of the group) and three females (42.9% of the group); the “out” group was comprised of three males (60% of the group) and two females (40% of the group). Ultimately, the results are based on an overall sample that has slightly more known participants than unknown, and slightly more males than females regardless of the cohort. Using a gerund-stems method, there were 15 total roots used accompanied by a total of 41 possible codes. Some roots had as few as one code associated, while others had as many as five. On average, each root possessed 2.7 possible codes. Table 2 shows all the root and code combinations generated.

Next, I present the frequency of codes used by participants organized in response to each research question, including reference to subgroups for the data set (“in” group, “out” group, male and female).

Table 2. Gerund Roots with Associated Codes

Gerund Roots	Associated Codes
Being	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient and/or flexible • Available outside of school hours • Firm but fair • Welcoming and understanding of circumstances • Willing to ask and listen
Having	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empathy/compassion • Their own style • Rigorous expectations
Showing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care/concern • That failure is ok • Students independence • Opportunities beyond high school
Taking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time to notice • Time to help
Wanting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kids to be successful • To teach for the kids • To see struggle
Pushing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Out of comfort zone • To be their best
Believing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In students' potential/dreams
Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grades more equitable • Things more accessible • A sense of community • An engaging learning environment
Involving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students' cultures/backgrounds • Parents/families
Checking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In on students' well-being, best interest
Connecting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With students • With parents
Giving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Space for student voices • Incentives • Opportunities to make up missing assignments • Opportunities to retake assessments • Specific/tailored feedback
Providing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools/resources to be successful • Representative books • Positive reinforcement
Emphasizing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance/value of education • Effort
Helping	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students realize their potential • Navigate college preparation

First Research Question

My first Research Question was: What personal qualities or characteristics do FGL students value most in their White teachers? The interviews were analyzed for the following reoccurring themes in response to Research Question 1, with Table 3 showing the frequency of codes delineated by cohort (“in” versus “out” group). The “in” group represented 58.3% of the participant total; the “out” group represented 41.7%.

In general, there were codes identified up to 20 times in relation to Research Question 1, with an average of 6.3 occurrences per code. The overall proportion of codes identified in response to Research Question 1 broke down very closely to the composition of the overall pool of participants (“in” and “out” members). Many of the possible codes were identified in relative proportion to the size of the cohort being examined as well; for example, “Having empathy/compassion” was used 60% of the time by the “in” group and 40% of the time by the “out” group, nearly matching the proportion of participants in those two groups (58.3% “in,” 41.7% “out”). There were several codes that only occurred in either one cohort or the other, but not in both. These include phrases such as “Being firm but fair” and “Wanting kids to be successful” lent exclusively to the “in” group, and phrases such as “Wanting to see struggle” and “Pushing to be their best” exclusive to the “out” group. In total, there were seven gerund stem codes that were used exclusively by one group or the other. One code that skewed disproportionately in frequency to the “out” group was “Being welcoming and understanding of circumstances.” The “out” group represented 55% of this code’s frequency, a bit higher than their overall proportion of participants (again, 41.7%).

Next, Table 4 shows the frequency of codes delineated by sex (male compared to female respondents). Males represented 58.3% of the participant total; females represented 41.7%.

Table 3. Frequency of Codes Used (by “In” Versus “Out” Cohort)

Gerund	Code (total)	Frequency (“in” group)	Frequency (“out” group)
Being	Patient and/or flexible (17)	12	5
	Available outside of school hours (15)	9	6
	Firm but fair (3)	3	0
	Welcoming and understanding of circumstances (20)	9	11
	Willing to ask and listen (1)	1	1
Having	Empathy/compassion (20)	12	8
	Their own style (1)	1	0
	Rigorous expectations (9)	6	3
Showing	Care/concern (1)	1	0
	That failure is ok (3)	1	2
	Students independence (1)	0	1
	Opportunities beyond high school (5)	3	2
Taking	Time to notice (5)	3	2
	Time to help (6)	3	3
Wanting	Kids to be successful (1)	1	0
	To teach for the kids (3)	1	2
	To see struggle (1)	0	1
Pushing	Out of comfort zone (4)	3	1
	To be their best (1)	0	1
Believing	In students’ potential/dreams (9)	6	3
Total codes (126)		75 (59.5%)	51 (40.5%)

Table 4. Frequency of Codes Used (by Male Versus Female Cohort)

Gerund	Code (total)	Frequency ("in" group)	Frequency ("out" group)
Being	Patient and/or flexible (17)	7	10
	Available outside of school hours (15)	9	6
	Firm but fair (3)	3	0
	Welcoming and understanding of circumstances (20)	12	8
	Willing to ask and listen (1)	0	1
Having	Empathy/compassion (20)	13	7
	Their own style (1)	1	0
	Rigorous expectations (9)	1	8
Showing	Care/concern (1)	1	0
	That failure is ok (3)	2	1
	Students independence (1)	1	0
	Opportunities beyond high school (5)	5	0
Taking	Time to notice (5)	4	1
	Time to help (6)	6	0
Wanting	Kids to be successful (1)	1	0
	To teach for the kids (3)	2	1
	To see struggle (1)	1	0
Pushing	Out of comfort zone (4)	2	2
	To be their best (1)	1	0
Believing	In students' potential/dreams (9)	2	7
Total codes (126)		74 (58.7%)	52 (41.3%)

The overall proportion of codes identified in the empathy interviews broke down almost identically to the composition of the overall pool of participants vis-à-vis the “in” and “out” members. Many of these possible codes were also identified in relative proportion to the size of the cohort being examined; for example, “Being welcoming and understanding of circumstances” was used 60% of the time by the male group and 40% of the time by the female group, nearly matching the proportion of participants in those two groups (58.3% male, 41.7% female). There was one code that only occurred in the female cohort but not in the male one. This included the phrase “Being willing to ask and listen.” There were nine codes that only appeared in the male cohort’s responses, including phrases such as “Being firm but fair,” “Showing care/concern,” and “Showing opportunities beyond high school.” Two codes that skewed disproportionately in frequency to the female group were “Being patient and/or flexible” and “Believing in students’ potential/dreams.” The female group represented 58.9% and 77.8% of these codes’ frequencies, higher than their overall 41.7% proportion of participants.

High Frequency Responses

The following codes occurred the most often and therefore represent high frequency responses:

- Being welcoming and understanding of circumstances (20)
- Having empathy/compassion (20)
- Being patient and/or flexible (17)
- Being available outside of school hours (15)

In response to Research Question 1, high frequency responses centered around gerund stems of “Being” and “Having.” More specifically, they involved understanding, empathy, patience, and availability. Participants spoke about this in different ways. Miguel said, “I just remember he was very patient.” Jose reminisced about teachers that “were always so welcoming, understanding.” Another participant, Maria, spoke about how she uses what she appreciated in her teachers now that she is a teacher herself. She said, “I go to them...like ‘Hey, if something comes up, come and talk to me. I’m also human so I understand that things will happen.’”

When asked what qualities they wanted districts and administrators to look for in teachers, respondents spoke regularly about empathy. Bruno stated that he hoped teachers would “empathize with students and get to know them.” Violet said she “would like to hire a teacher for their being empathetic more than anything.” Similarly, Patty said: “I think the biggest quality that makes a great teacher...the difference is the compassion.” Janira mentioned empathy multiple times, remembering that “the teachers [she] connected with most were those who were empathetic.” She also stated that she tried to embody that now “as an educator.”

Medium Frequency Responses

The following codes occurred moderately often and therefore represent medium frequency responses:

- Having rigorous expectations (9)
- Believing in students’ potential/dreams (9)
- Taking time to help (6)
- Showing opportunities beyond high school (5)
- Taking time to notice (5)

In response to Research Question 1, medium frequency responses included gerund stems such as “Having,” “Believing,” “Taking” and “Showing.” More specifically, they involved taking time, believing in students, and having high expectations. Jose juxtaposed many teachers that he felt “just don’t look to happy being there sometimes” with those he appreciated who “really took time to notice” when he needed something. Another participant, Patty, spoke about the impact of “a teacher who does take that, you know, interest or who sees that potential and is trying to help you meet that potential...that really makes a big difference.”

Respondents also spoke about appreciating teachers who had high expectations. Maria reflected on an impactful teacher who “taught [her] about being rigorous and consistent.” Ashley remembered a teacher who “taught us structure, like, discipline when it came to...homework and stuff like that.”

Similarly, Bruno said he sometimes wished there “were stricter policies where they weren’t as lenient with [him].” Another interviewee appreciated a teacher who she “didn’t wanna let down” because she knew “he expected a lot of you.”

Low Frequency Responses

The following codes occurred rarely and therefore represented low frequency responses:

- Pushing out of comfort zone (4)
- Being firm but fair (3)
- Showing that failure is ok (3)
- Wanting to teach for the kids (3)
- Being willing to ask and listen (1)
- Having their own style (1)
- Showing care/concern (1)
- Showing students independence (1)
- Wanting kids to be successful (1)
- Wanting to see struggle (1)
- Pushing to be their best (1)

In response to Research Question 1, low frequency responses covered a wide variety of gerund stems. Some that appeared more than once include “Pushing out of comfort zone” and “Showing that failure is ok.” Eric appreciated an elementary school teacher because “she pushed me to try to get out of my comfort zone.” He added that “it wasn’t like a force, it was more naturally.” Maria reported that it helped “having grades where it leans towards students being able to learn and grow” from their mistakes.

Second Research Question

My second research question was: What classroom policies or practices do FGL students find beneficial when implemented by White teachers? The interviews were analyzed for the following

reoccurring themes in response to Research Question 2, with Table 5 showing the frequency of codes delineated by cohort (“in” versus “out” group). Again, the “in” group represented 58.3% of the participant total; the “out” group represented 41.7%.

Table 5. Frequency of Codes Used (by “In” Versus “Out” Cohort)

Gerund	Code (total)	Frequency (“in” group)	Frequency (“out” group)
Making	Grades more equitable (2)	1	1
	Things more accessible (6)	5	1
	A sense of community (7)	5	2
	An engaging learning environment (2)	2	0
Involving	Students’ cultures/backgrounds (9)	9	0
	Parents/families (3)	1	2
Checking	In on students’ well-being, best interest (9)	4	5
Connecting	With students (7)	6	1
	With parents (2)	1	1
Giving	Space for student voices (8)	6	2
	Incentives (5)	5	0
	Opportunities to make up missing assignments (2)	0	2
	Opportunities to retake assessments (2)	2	0
	Specific/tailored feedback (3)	0	3
Providing	Tools/resources to be successful (8)	6	2
	Representative books (1)	1	0
	Positive Reinforcement (2)	0	2
Emphasizing	Importance/value of education (2)	1	1
	Effort (2)	0	2
Helping	Students realize their potential (5)	3	2
	Navigate college preparation (5)	0	5
Total codes (92)		58 (63%)	34 (37%)

In general, there were fewer codes identified in response to this Research Question 2 (92) than Research Question 1 (126). In addition, there were no codes identified more than nine times in relation to Research Question 2, with an average of 4.4 occurrences per code. The overall proportion of codes identified in response to Research Question 2 broke closely to the composition of the overall pool of participants (“in” and “out” members). Most of the possible codes skewed disproportionately one way or another; for example, “Making things more accessible” was used 83.3% of the time by the “in” group and only 16.7% of the time by the “out” group, tilting much more in volume compared to the overall composition (58.3% “in,” 41.7% “out”). There were several codes that only occurred in either one cohort or the other, but not in both. These include phrases such as “Involving students’ cultures/backgrounds” and “Giving incentives” used exclusively by the “in” group, and phrases such as “Giving opportunities to make up assignments” and “Giving specific/tailored feedback” exclusive to the “out” group. In total, there were 10 gerund stem codes that were used exclusively by one group or the other, representing nearly half of all codes identified in relation to Research Question 2 when delineated by “in” and “out” cohorts.

Next, Table 6 showed the frequency of codes delineated by sex (male compared to female respondents). Again, males represented 58.3% of the participant total; females represented 41.7%.

The overall proportion of codes identified in response to Research Question 2 was overrepresented by male respondents (71.7% of responses compared to being 58.3% of the group). Female respondents were responsible for only 28.3% of these codes compared to being 41.7% of the participant pool. A few codes skewed disproportionately from the female cohort; for example, responses such as “Connecting with students” and “Giving specific/tailored feedback” were given by both male and female participants, but more frequently by female participants despite their smaller proportion of the overall group. There were several codes that only occurred in either one cohort or the other, but not in both. These included phrases such as “Making grades more equitable” and “Giving incentives” used exclusively by the male respondents, and phrases such as “Giving opportunities to retake assessments” and “Providing positive reinforcement” exclusive to the female participants. In total, there were eight gerund stem codes that were used exclusively by one group or the other.

Table 6. Frequency of Codes Used (by Male Versus Female Cohort)

Gerund	Code (total)	Frequency ("in" group)	Frequency ("out" group)
Making	Grades more equitable (2)	2	0
	Things more accessible (6)	4	2
	A sense of community (7)	6	1
	An engaging learning environment (2)	1	1
Involving	Students' cultures/backgrounds (9)	7	2
	Parents/families (3)	2	1
Checking	In on students' well-being, best interest (9)	7	2
Connecting	With students (7)	3	4
	With parents (2)	1	1
Giving	Space for student voices (8)	7	1
	Incentives (5)	5	0
	Opportunities to make up missing assignments (2)	2	0
	Opportunities to retake assessments (2)	0	2
	Specific/tailored feedback (3)	1	2
Providing	Tools/resources to be successful (8)	7	1
	Representative books (1)	1	0
	Positive Reinforcement (2)	0	2
Emphasizing	Importance/value of education (2)	2	0
	Effort (2)	2	0
Helping	Students realize their potential (5)	4	1
	Navigate college preparation (5)	2	3
Total codes (92)		66 (71.7%)	26 (28.3%)

High Frequency Responses

The following codes occurred the most often and therefore represent high frequency responses:

- Involving students' cultures/backgrounds (9)
- Checking in on students' well-being, best interest (9)
- Giving space for student voices (8)
- Providing tools/resources to be successful (8)
- Making a sense of community (7)
- Connecting with students (7)

In response to Research Question 2, high frequency responses included various gerund stems, with “Involving students' cultures/backgrounds,” and “Checking in on students' well-being, best interest” being the most common. One example was Jose, who appreciated when a teacher would “just ask me how my life is going, because I feel like the biggest thing you can do with kids is to earn their trust.” Another participant, Bruno, spoke about how he felt when White teachers failed to involve his background. He said it felt like “they didn't know the culture, and to them it was just a job.”

Another common theme was an appreciation for teachers who managed their classrooms in ways that gave space for student voices. Miguel recalled that “because we had those little discussions...I was more inclined to actually like wanna participate in the class.” Eric appreciated teachers that “gave [him] chances and opportunities to talk in the classroom.” Participants also emphasized connection and community. Miguel remembered how “everyone just meshed so well together and it was like this little family.” Violet valued White teachers “creating a healthy classroom environment where everyone's allowed to share and not be cut off.”

Participants also described their appreciation for teachers who were intentional about connecting with students. Maria compared teachers who were solely focused on the academics and content to those who made connections; she said, “the teachers that really put in the effort to...get to know where we came from or like what's going on...those were the teachers I remember the most.”

Medium Frequency Responses

The following codes occurred moderately often and therefore represent medium frequency responses:

- Making things more accessible (6)
- Giving incentives (5)
- Helping students realize their potential (5)
- Helping navigate college preparation (5)

In response to Research Question 2, medium frequency responses centered around gerund stems of “Making,” “Giving” and “Helping.” More specifically, they involved accessibility and incentives. Speaking to accessibility, Bruno recalled feeling helped and supported when teachers would clearly articulate “okay, this is what you need to do and this is how you do it.” Regarding incentives, Mario was wistful when recalling competition; he said, “these kinds of challenges always excited me, and if they were rewarded by teachers I think it just further incentivized me.”

Low Frequency Responses

The following codes occurred rarely and therefore represent low frequency responses:

- Involving parents/families (3)
- Giving specific/tailored feedback (3)
- Making grades more equitable (2)
- Making an engaging learning environment (2)
- Connecting with parents (2)
- Giving opportunities to make up missing assignments (2)
- Giving opportunities to retake assessments (2)
- Providing positive reinforcement (2)
- Emphasizing importance/value of education (2)

- Emphasizing effort (2)
- Providing representative books (1)

In response to Research Question 2, low frequency responses covered a wide variety of themes. Common gerund stems included “Giving,” “Making,” and “Emphasizing.” Giving second chances, both on assignments and assessments, was mentioned a few times. Maria appreciated “the ability to have students do retakes...for a quiz....if you didn’t get something right the first time, relearn it....study it and then come back and retake the quiz.” Jose also appreciated it when he might have missed an assignment “but there’s still opportunities to kind of earn it back.”

Summary

Chapter 4 begins with a general overview of the findings, which included discussion of the following distinct cohorts: “in” group and “out” group participants, male and female respondents. This was followed by a description of the gerund stem system used for data collection, including a complete table of all codes generated by me from all of the empathy interviews. Next, I organized codes by Research Question, providing tables that indicated the gerund stem, code, and frequency. This was delineated by both cohort divisions (“in” versus “out” and male compared to female).

For Research Question 1, the most common themes about teachers’ qualities included “Being welcoming and understanding of circumstances” and “Having empathy/compassion.” Most codes occurred in relative proportion to the size of the sample, however some responses occurred only in one group and not another, such as “Being firm but fair.” In addition, some codes arose at a higher rate than the proportion of the cohort. For example, “Being welcoming and understanding of circumstances” was reported by the “out” group at a rate higher than their makeup of the overall total participants.

For Research Question 2, the most common themes regarding teachers’ actions included “Involving students’ cultures/backgrounds” and “Checking in on students’ well-being, best interest.” Overall, there were fewer codes identified in response to this question than the first. Also, the overall proportion of codes identified in response to this question was overrepresented by male respondents and

there were several gerund stem codes that occurred only in one cohort but not another, such as “Giving incentives” and “Giving specific/tailored feedback.”

Finally, I provided examples of participant responses (using pseudonyms) to deliver rich descriptions using and amplifying their own words. Samples were provided from all cohort members, including “in” and “out” groups as well as both male and female participants. In the next chapter, I provide an analysis and interpretation of the findings described in this chapter.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION

Though not always as blatantly symbolic as literal railroad tracks creating the separation in some places, there exists historical gaps in educational outcomes for many different student-groups. Whether grouped by race and ethnicity or by socio-economic status, non-White and non-affluent students consistently underperform their White and financially stable peers (Lareau, 2003; Portes & MacLeod, 1996). The problem this study addressed was the persistent disparity in outcomes for FGL students, using a lens illuminated by their reported preferences of what helped them feel capable and deserving of success throughout their K-12 education. Importantly, the framework for looking at this problem was rooted in the relationship between a majority Latinx student body and an overwhelmingly White teaching force.

The purpose of this qualitative study was to discover the qualities and practices of White teachers that FGL students value and appreciate; additionally, the purpose was to highlight and amplify the voices and words of the students themselves. The study addressed two research questions:

1. What personal qualities or characteristics do FGL students value most in their White teachers?
2. What classroom policies or practices do FGL students find beneficial when implemented by White teachers?

The study was performed by conducting “empathy interviews” with several first-generation Latinx high school graduates. Their responses were coded and organized thematically, providing insight into their perspectives and preferences. Knowing this information will help district and site administrators both paper-screen and look for these qualities and practices in their interviewing and hiring processes, as well as help them cultivate these qualities and practices in existing teaching staff through intentional PD.

This chapter offers my interpretation of what conclusions can be extracted from the data and findings enumerated in Chapter 4. It also provided discussion of potential implications at the school site

level and beyond, and suggested recommendations for policies, practices, and additional future research. I want to amplify the voices of participants, so this chapter will be rife with quotes from their interviews.

Conclusions

From my findings I have drawn several conclusions about what is important to know about FGL students and their K-12 education: first, FGL students care far more about *who their teachers are* than *how they teach*; second, FGL students need empathy, patience, compassion and understanding above all else; and third, failure to intentionally train White teachers how to incorporate students' culture, background and interests is a dereliction of duty on the part of schools and districts.

“Who” versus “How”

Throughout my interviews—with both known and unknown subjects and both male and female participants—responses overwhelmingly referred to specific qualities and characteristics of White teachers that they appreciated, remembered, and valued. In fact, even when asked questions about classroom policies and practices, respondents frequently responded in ways that continued to describe the manner or demeanor of their teachers, rather than concrete practices or execution of policy. An interesting note that may be rooted in biological and sociological differences attributed to gender normative expectations is that the male participants were much more apt to give responses that ended up being coded as actions or things others “should do.” They felt comfortable giving advice. Ultimately, many of the responses still fell under the umbrella of Research Question 1.

For perspective, despite the interview questions being evenly divided between seeking answers to the two unique research questions, the volume of responses that participants expressed in ways that connected thematically and with consistency when coding transcripts were germane to Research Question 1 (about teachers' qualities and characteristics). There were a total of 126 coded responses to Research Question 1, and only 92 coded responses to Research Question 2. On Research Question 1, 45% of responses focused on just a few preferred traits (those will be discussed specifically in the next section); on Research Question 2, while ostensibly about policy and practice, respondents gave answers

35% of the time that also required those same characteristics in order to be implemented effectively. Even when talking about what teachers did in class, participants were more grateful for and impacted by *the way in which they were carried out* than by what the actual practice or policy was.

This comports with existing research about improved achievement for Latinx students who felt welcomed and valued (Garza, 2009; Perez, 2000). It also aligns with findings in terms of what happens when teachers treat Latinx students with an asset-based mindset, manifested in respectful and caring treatment (Perez, 2000; López, 2016). In addition, in alignment with the findings of Allen et al. (2016), participants that felt a sense of belonging in their classrooms indicated that as a reason for wanting to work hard and for feeling a sense of their own potential. Jose said it helped when teachers would,

have...personal talks, like they didn't even have be about school sometimes. Just ask me...how my life is going, cause I feel like the biggest thing you can do with kids is to earn their trust, cause I feel like when a kid feels like they're being heard...they're more inclined to do more.

The sense of safety and being cared for was another resonant theme, which mirrors findings by Perez (2000) and López (2016). Mario described in detail what it felt like when this was *not* the case:

...destroyed, I think trust which may not destroy it, but definitely injured the trust that they would have as students. And I think with some first-generation students, they might already feel vulnerable. They might already feel intimidated, especially by positions of power that they're not accustomed to, or that seem foreign to them. And having a teacher that's not that empathetic where we can show empathy or patience during critical moments could really damage the trust that otherwise these first-generation students might have with the teachers that would allow them to grow as students.

He continued by sharing what that did to his comfort and willingness to ask for help. He described it by saying “it almost became shameful, I think, to keep going over and over and ask for help, which kind of just made a cycle of getting left behind.” Under the auspices of “tough love” or “high expectations” (maybe because “I was taught that way” among other reasons), many White teachers alienate their FGL students and not only fail to support their academic growth, but actively exacerbate the challenges they experience in the first place. Ashley shared a closely related anecdote about what happened to her when she did not feel welcomed or valued in a class: “I wouldn't really ask by...the end

of the school year...like I wouldn't ask for help.” She continued, “Luckily I had friends in that in that class that would help me out. But I wouldn't....I wouldn't go to that teacher.”

Jose similarly described what he perceived when teachers behaved in that way, saying “it's actually like it was a couple of teachers, sadly, where they really took the time to notice, like lots of them just don't look too happy being there sometimes.” He continued to describe his perception, stating “I think it was more what they didn't do. I just didn't feel like they didn't care whether I was there right, whether I passed or failed.” Along those same lines, Maria articulated what it felt like when teachers seem fixated on academic curriculum at the expense of personal connection. Maria is a teacher now, and she said “you spend so much time worrying about like whether your students are gonna do well in the class, but not prioritizing who they are. They're never gonna do good 'cause they don't care.”

With hundreds of pages of transcripts and explicit research questions searching in equal part for what classroom policies and practices FGL students valued and appreciated, not a single respondent positively recollected a specific assignment related to any curriculum. They did not much emphasize class rules or routines either, outside of an appreciation for some flexibility, which will be addressed more deeply in the following section.

What they did remember was who their teachers were at their core, assessed in terms of how they made students feel. Not only were they more likely to work hard and achieve success *for* certain teachers, but the opposite impact was also prevalent. When their White teachers failed to seek understanding or invest in authentic relationships, participants became less likely to put in effort and in fact became reluctant to ask questions or seek help. This is adjacent to research regarding circumstantial struggles and the burden they cause on FGL students which was worsened when they become uncomfortable seeking help from their teachers (Friedrich, 2015; Rosenthal, 1987). The next section will address the common themes that represented a vast majority of responses from all participants, regardless of which group they represent in the sample.

Empathy, Patience, Compassion, Understanding

There were three codes responsible for nearly half (45%) of all responses to Research Question 1; these included “Being welcoming and understanding of circumstances,” “Having empathy/compassion,” and “Being patient and/or flexible.” In response to Research Question 2, there were four codes that can be interpreted as referring to teachers’ traits in how they implemented practices, which accounted for 35% of all responses in relation to that question, including “Involving students’ cultures/backgrounds,” “Checking in on students’ well-being, best interest,” “Making a sense of community,” and “Connecting with students.” Overall, a mere 17% of themed codes represented almost half (41%) of all responses and can be categorized into four main qualities: empathy, patience, compassion, and understanding.

Many respondents referred to empathy specifically and directly. Miguel simply stated that the most important thing he needed from his White teachers was, “I think, empathy is the biggest one. It's just. It's something that's helped me a lot. It's just, put yourself in in their shoes.” When asked the same question, Bruno said “empathize with students and get to know them....Be personable. Know their background family-wise. Don't just assume.” Another participant, Barry, described the impact that a lack of empathy had on him. In terms of teachers who made him feel valued, he said,

I think a large number did build me up, but I do remember a few that like didn't really care. They're just like, I don't care that you have this other stuff, and I don't care what you have going on outside of school. It just matters what [you're] doing my class....And so those also leave a mark in a negative way.

Later, Barry continued to talk about compassion, emphasizing,

I think compassion and empathy are like probably the top things that you need to like have as a teacher. This is the teacher that I remember the most that like not just, they taught me well, but they showed compassion towards me, and they showed like empathy and care like they tried to like, connect with me as like a person like, instead of just like only as a student.

Importantly, he followed up with these words: “Those are the teachers that I remember the most.” Like all interviewees in this study, the impact of his treatment far outweighed any assignment or class rule that was ever implemented.

One essential distinction in terms of students’ recall of this quality is their desire for empathy, and not sympathy. None of my interviewees expressed a hope that any of their teachers felt sorry for them, or “took it easy” on them due to their circumstances. They appreciated high expectations, but they needed the gray area that is afforded by empathy and patience.

Additional participants emphasized similar themes. Janira, who became a teacher herself, described appreciating her White teachers,

who are more empathetic. I think empathy is a big thing. Just kind, more passionate, like. I think students really read off of that, like, they know when a teacher's passionate, when they kind of are flexible, like, I said. Just empathy when they understand like they're going through something, you know, and I take that as well as an educator.

She also referenced the value of patience, describing what would help when missing an assignment:

Now, like, you know, it's not the end of the world if they had something going on, and they didn't turn in like one assignment. You know, it's kind of realizing it's not the biggest priority in their life all the time.

When asked about what she wanted most from her teachers, she said:

I would say to just like be flexible....I don't know why I keep saying it, but just like empathy is a big thing. and I think the teachers that I connected most were those who were like empathetic to me. And that's what I remember most. Those that I remember when I was going through like hard things... I remember that like gave me leniency, even offered me like a hug and just words of encouragement.

That reference to leniency appeared several times as participants recollected how much they needed it at times due to circumstances beyond their control or challenges that made work completion and studying very difficult. This reflected research done around “coercive isomorphism” and its impact on students of color who were being held to rules and expectations made by White teachers that are more difficult for non-White students to meet due to exacerbating circumstances, such as the need to work after school to help the family pay bills or to care for siblings so that parents could work additional

hours (Beckert, 2010). Janira referenced this lived experience, stating “Not everybody has the opportunity to just go home, sit somewhere quiet and do homework and study.” Juan recommended that teachers “Just ask questions. You know, everybody's every situation is different. You can't provide advice and tailor solutions if you don't know who's sitting across from you.” White teachers need to have an awareness that the students they teach are having a very different lived experience than they had, which will be addressed in the next section. This related closely to the importance of understanding, which is something participants referenced often in moving detail.

Something that was surprising through this process was how many of the subjects became emotional during the interview, with nearly half of all participants crying at some point during their session. This was a profound reminder that they were not sharing mere *preferences*, but rather what they perceived as *needs* for FGL students to feel a sense of belonging and success in school. One important potential limitation here was due to the nature of my relationship with several of the participants. Some of them mentioned specifically when answering questions, and it is certainly possible that they remembered things more fondly due to our relationship. This could be supported by the fact that while several participants teared up during the interview, only those who were part of the “in” group did so. Next, I will share powerful anecdotes that illustrate how vital a sense of understanding of circumstances is to FGL students.

One story was shared by Eric, as he remembered what it felt like to be “other” than his White or affluent classmates:

I was very embarrassed. I was very embarrassed to invite and hang out with friends. During my middle school years especially just because I felt like my friends wouldn't accept me during that time, because, you know they all lived in houses, and I was living in a mobile home. And it's one of those things where it felt weird to try to, you know, like they invite me all the time. But it's weird for me to, you know, tell them like, ‘Oh, yeah, come over.’ I share a room. They have their own rooms, and I share a room with my brothers and I don't even have my own bed. I have had to sleep on the couch or something.

While this is a more social anecdote, it is tied to an academic example shared by Maria that illuminated what certain assignments can feel like when a student is having a vastly different lived experience. She described an assignment for a Science class that by all accounts was well-intentioned, steeped in action-research and project-based learning. In this example, I also happen to know the teacher personally and I know her to be a strong ally for equity and someone who cares deeply about her students. Still, she had no idea what this assignment felt like to Maria. She described the experience this way:

I remember one time there was an assignment for that class where we had to explain, like how much carbon emissions like we utilize right. And I remember mine was so low. And that's 'cause my parents didn't own a car so like I would always walk, or I would take the bus to places like stuff like that. And I remember one time like when we had to share with our group members like what our emission total was, like everyone theirs was super high. They're all like, 'oh, I have a car. Me and my family go here. We go there. We travel here, so we use a lot of emissions over here over there,' and like I remember the person I was partners with [saying] 'there's no way yours is so low like, don't you like travel, go places and everything like that?' And I remember that was the first moment I was like, oh, yeah, like I didn't wanna tell them that my parents didn't own a car or something like that cause then I was like, then I feel...like I feel like I'd have to explain myself, and where I come from and to me....I didn't feel like sharing, because it wasn't comfortable. So I remember I just brushed it off and was like, oh, yeah, like, maybe I calculated it wrong, you know.

Maria described another similar experience rooted in lack of understanding from the same class, again highlighting the implicit nature of misunderstanding, as I am certain her teacher had no ill intention with the design of the lesson. She described that experience this way:

We were talking about how you had to buy groceries and you had to take a picture with your groceries, or the week in terms of like how much food we use. I don't know some assignment like that, and it was extra credit, and I needed help in that....So then, like, I sent a photo right. But it was like, and you were supposed to have your parents in the photo, too. But I just wanted to have my mom in the photo so like we just gathered like a couple of items that we had bought, and like I remember [the teacher] had said, like, 'Oh, do you want us to share the photos?' Once you send the photo, she would share it to the class if you wanted to, and I had said, no 'cause I didn't want other people to see like that....for my family, we buy groceries on a day-to-day basis, like we don't buy for a full week right? Mainly because it's like we buy necessities for the day. But I remember saying no to it. But then the next day, when she put up the photos of other individuals, and like how their families, like their tables, were full of like food and everything because they buy things for the week...I think that assignment kind of made me feel a little bad just because I was like, oh yeah, like again, my family. We only buy things that are necessary on a day-to-day basis like other people have the....luxury to be able to buy on like a weekly basis.

Once again, the inadvertent othering was unnoticed by the teacher but nevertheless had a negative impact on the student. It impacted the way she felt in relation to her White and affluent peers in the class and highlighted her sense of being “other” in that space.

Another example of implicit assumptions that had tangible impacts on FGL students was attributed to a response from Patty, when remembering certain assignments. She said she appreciated

Teachers who would assign...the type of homework that everybody could do, could have access to and not like have to buy other things like poster boards [which] were always so annoying that you know you had to tell your parents....You have to go buy...construction paper, and we have to print things. And you know we don't have a printer or anything like that like, how are we gonna do this?

The assumption that all students have the means (including money but also transportation and time) to complete certain assignments or access certain materials is another problem rooted in White teachers not understanding that their expectations of non-White students often exist without understanding the differences in lived experiences (Kohli & Pizarro, 2016). Those lived experiences involved sacrifices of time from FGL students that their peers do not experience which have a direct impact on their ability to keep up with coercively isomorphic policies and practices. For example, the need for many FGL males to work and pay bills, or for females to assist with childcare or volunteer to support their mom at work is well-known and affects those students' ability to give equal time and effort as their peers (Bernal & Domenech Rodriguez, 2009; Martinez et al., 2009; Nunez et al., 2013; O'Neal et al., 2016).

These examples highlighted the conceptual framework for this study. CRP—when used—made students' experiences more accessible and impactful, and when missing, exacerbated the feelings of alienation and inadequacy faced by FGL students. Conversely, the standards of expectation rooted in White “normalcy” amplified outcome disparities for FGL students, including the creation of environments that not only made them feel unwelcome, but that they actively sought to distance themselves from in response to those feelings. One takeaway is the importance of recognizing the nature of implicit bias, as many of the experiences shared by subjects of this study were arguably not done with

intent to harm. Nevertheless, the harm they experienced *was* real to them. Clearly, the lack of explicit amelioration of bias is a problem that needs to be addressed in and of itself.

An additional question that arises from these results in relation to the conceptual framework is whether or not the specific qualities and characteristics mentioned by these FGL subjects would be beneficial in *any* teacher, regardless of their ethnicity, race, or lived experience. Based on the interviews conducted as part of this research (the initial part of the empathy interview protocol asked about teachers generally prior to drilling down on White educators specifically), it was valid to say that these participants fondly remembered all their teachers who possessed these dispositions. Much like the philosophy underpinning universal design for learning in the special education world, good teachers and good teaching are simply good regardless of who it comes from.

However, there was a consistent throughline that showed participants' experiences with White teachers were still different than those with their teachers of color. White teachers did not inherently bring an understanding of the culture, experiences, and challenges faced by their FGL students without intentional and purposeful effort. In the words of this study's interviewees, FGL students felt understood inherently by their teachers from common backgrounds; this was not the case when they interacted with their White teachers and it required a more specific intentionality for them to feel valued, seen, and understood by those educators, thus reinforcing the premise of this study's conceptual framework highlighting the power of purposeful CRP to mitigate the negative effects (intentional or otherwise) that historical social dynamics created for FGL students.

Face the Problem Honestly and with Purpose

While it has fallen politically out of vogue recently, especially in EWUSD and other similar districts and geographic regions, the need to say forcefully and without equivocation that White teachers must learn about racially rooted implicit bias and how to mitigate it is a moral imperative that has become more important, not less so, in recent years. The student body being served by teachers across California is increasingly diverse, with Latinx students making a growing proportion with consistency.

Add to this the fact that, according to the CDE (2023), areas like Orange County have work forces comprised of 71.2% White teachers and a student body that is majority Latinx, we have to admit that those in front of the room do not look like nor have they lived like those in the desks (setting aside the fact that they should not spend much time in front of the room, either).

This final conclusion as a result of the study's data analysis is that FGL students need teachers who not only embodied the personal qualities and characteristics mentioned above, but who also recognized that they must acknowledge differences in their lived experiences compared to those of the students they serve and work consciously to reduce the ways in which biases negatively influence their relationships with students and the academic outcomes that follow.

Implications and Recommendations

Based on extensive data analysis and interpretation, there are three conclusions anchored in the study. FGL students care far more about the personal qualities and characteristics of their White teachers than they did about the classroom policies and practices that they implemented. In addition, the qualities and characteristics that they do value the most can be described as empathy, patience, compassion and understanding. Finally, it is essential that White teachers are provided explicit conversation and work around the negative impacts of implicit bias on these students and how to mitigate those effects. Such conclusions give rise to several important implications and recommendations for both educational policy and practice.

Implications and Recommendations for Policy

As a result of this qualitative study, I have determined two implications for policy, and have offered recommendations for ways to support these changes.

Teachers Should Cultivate Awareness of Desired Characteristics

Discussion of the specifically named dispositions found in this study—empathy, patience, compassion and understanding—needs to be explicit, reflected upon, and measured. While the teaching force will likely become more diverse and intentional efforts at the university level create more just,

equitable and inclusive outcomes, there are decades of systemic racism to overcome. Not only that, but the *current* teaching force has remained overwhelmingly White; this makes it all the more important for teachers across the K-12 spectrum to be required to confront implicit bias and learn how they can support their diverse student population with purpose.

Recommendations to Cultivate Awareness

Districts and site leaders need to be given space and time to teach their staff about the reality of privilege and the myth of meritocracy; this can be done with sensitivity to the reality that so many White teachers do well and mean well and do not *consciously* contribute to the perpetuation of disparate outcomes (Vaught & Castagno, 2008). If the skill (or will) is not present within a district, highly regarded experts in the field of implicit bias and culturally relevant pedagogy should be brought in to facilitate this work. It could begin at the district office level and then be rolled out to teachers, or events such as the return-to-work meeting (“Convocation” in some places) could be a place to roll it out districtwide at once.

This undoubtedly required courageous leadership because the backlash will be quick, and it will be loud. But we cannot turn a blind eye to the fact that Latinx students continue to experience deteriorating experiences and outcomes in the face of the status quo (Guyll et al., 2010). As Roy T. Bennett said, we must “Do what is right, not what is easy nor what is popular.”

Principals Should Hire for Empathy, Patience, Compassion and Understanding

Knowing these are the characteristics that former students highlighted in their own words, we should ensure that we are looking for those qualities at the earliest possible stages of the hiring process.

Recommendations to Hire for Specific Demeanor

Teacher interviews should include at least one question about how candidates connect with students from cultural backgrounds different than their own. While a 15-minute interview is not remotely enough time to truly get to know a candidate’s core values and defining disposition, asking at least one question that explicitly targets the topic of serving a diverse student population would give site

principals at least a glimpse into whether a potential new staff member is already mindful or intentional around this work.

Districts need to work closely with the appropriate associations to negotiate this kind of language into the interview process. They need to be clear about the need to do work to counteract disproportionate outcomes in academics, discipline, and overall achievement that have plagued the Latinx contingent of schools in southern California for decades (Benner & Graham, 2011; Farkas, 2003; Gándara & Contreras, 2009; Peguero & Shekarkhar, 2011; Skiba et al., 2011).

After interviews were completed, principals should lead their guiding coalition in a reflective conversation about whether or not any candidates showed evidence of having these preferred qualities and characteristics; it should be an explicit conversation that is done in balance with any other practical considerations such as content knowledge or experience. Pedagogy can be taught, character much less so (if at all).

Implications and Recommendations for Practice

Based on this qualitative study, I have also identified two implications for practice. I offer recommendations for ways to implement these changes as well.

Principals Need to Incorporate Culturally Responsive Pedagogy into Their Yearlong PD plans

While the degree of control principals have over agendas for weekly and monthly meetings varies from district to district, whatever control they do have needs to be leveraged to ensure that work on culturally relevant pedagogy was embedded into the work done as a staff to improve instruction and school climate.

Recommendations to Embed CRP into Site PD

From the start of the year, principals should be expecting their teachers to know their students by name, face and story. They can print rosters with columns for teachers to fill in as they get to know their students with categories ranging from surface level: are they emerging bilingual, if so what is their ELPAC overall level, what are some of their favorites (food, music, movie, YouTuber, etc.); to deeper

and more intimate knowledge: What do they want to be when they grow up? Who lives in their house (relationships, divorce, etc.)? What does their room look like?

As teachers “peel the onion” to the deeper layers, they will begin to understand their students better and they should begin to treat them with the empathy, patience, compassion and understanding as their actual former students have stated clearly was most important to them. Students who feel “seen” and validated will be more likely to persevere academically and behave in ways that their teacher expected of them. Teachers can and should incorporate their knowledge of surface level details into their lessons—making a reference to a favorite soccer player can get the attention of even the most distracted young scholar—and use the deeper knowledge to foster authentic relationships with students that transcend curriculum and instruction.

Principals can also be intentional about learning the culture of their community and passing that knowledge to teachers. Do they know when Mother’s Day is in Mexico? Do they know what the *Posada* is? What is the difference between Cinco de Mayo and Mexican Independence Day in September? What is a *chancla* used for? Do they know about la Llorona or el Cucuy? Beyond that, do they know what values many traditional Latinx households maintained in terms of family and loyalty? How are males and females treated differently? When White teachers show students and families that they are trying to learn about their culture, they build relationships that can be leveraged to push students to work hard, to believe in themselves, and to secure more just, equitable and inclusive outcomes for themselves and their families.

Principals Need to Hold Teachers Accountable When They Fail to treat Students with Empathy and Compassion

It is difficult for principals to hold teachers accountable even for egregious violations of professional practice, but it is important for them to try to do so. As Frederik Backman said, “Culture isn’t just what we encourage but what we allow to happen.” Principals need to call out a lack of empathy when it occurs, whether in individual interactions with teachers or in group settings.

Recommendations to Hold Teachers Accountable

Principals need help from their district leaders when it comes to negotiating with the Association. Human resource leads can assist by maintaining open dialogue with Association leads, with transparency about the importance of how adults treat children. As part of the work required to generate a more just and equitable environment for Latinx students, they need to inform them that principals will have an acute lens for the treatment of those students to ensure responsiveness to their unique needs.

Work also needs to be done that makes it easier to move teachers to less diverse sites if they show consistently that they do not possess the empathy, patience and understanding that students need, particularly when serving a predominantly Latinx student body. Such sites need teachers with the patient disposition—desired by FGL students in their own words in this study—more than other places do, and the gap in achievement and outcomes will never close if we continue to allow those who do not possess the right demeanor to remain at sites where they are not a fit.

Recommendations for Future Research

The findings of this study illuminate the need for additional research around how teachers have come about the dispositions described consistently by FGL students as well as how teachers developed the repertoire and decided to implement the practices described by participants throughout this study. Is it a “chicken and egg” conundrum? Do certain dispositions find themselves becoming educators? If so, why do respondents indicate that it was lacking in so many of their teachers? Can the dispositions be developed further? If so, how or in what ways? Regarding practices, do some teachers know of them but choose not to use them? If so, why not? Or, do they merely lack the training or exposure to these practices? If so, what is the best way to ensure that skill gap is filled?

A qualitative study asking White teachers what they do to support FGL students would be valuable, especially juxtaposed to this study; it would be enlightening to see if and when there was overlap between what teachers believe about themselves and what they were doing vis-à-vis and what students perceived them as being and doing. Lastly, it can be argued that some of the findings in this

study in relation to White teachers could be valuable when possessed or implemented by any teachers, regardless of their cultural, racial, or ethnic background. Further research that purposefully compares FGL students' perceptions and value placed on the dispositions, policies and practices of their White teachers vis-à-vis their teachers of color would be important in distinguishing if these findings apply exclusively to White teachers or to all teachers more broadly.

Summary of the Dissertation

In neighborhoods all across southern California, the sounds of Banda and the smells of grilled asada permeate apartment walls or travel door-to-door across pre-fabricated mobile homes. The joy that those sensations can represent is tainted by the stress of two families sharing one space, of children with no room or bed to call their own, and of the specter of eviction constantly on the horizon. While the uncertainty that accompanies low-wage hourly labor and the toxic stress of economic uncertainty—coupled with children emerging as bilingual but forced into a monolingual school system—the challenges posed by this state of living are profound. Yet, students from circumstances exactly like this find ways to be successful in school and beyond.

This qualitative study asked FGL students from environments just like that what they valued and appreciated in their teachers throughout their K-12 school experience. More specifically, the study asked them to focus on their White teachers—in disposition and practice—and how those teachers found ways to make them feel welcomed, valued, and capable. Importantly, this study highlighted the voices and stories of the participants; this is *their* study.

Three ultimate conclusions were pulled from the analysis of data cultivated through empathy interviews. First, FGL students care far more about the demeanor of their teachers than the instructional practices and classroom policies they utilized. Second, FGL students implored teachers to bring empathy, patience, compassion and understanding to students above all else; and third, it was incumbent upon educational institutions entrusted to serve these students to train White teachers with intention and purpose on how to incorporate students' culture, background and interests. These conclusions

necessitate an attempt to make changes in both policy and practice. Purposeful attention to the identification and cultivation of preferred characteristics is needed. District and site level leaders need to speak concretely about the value of these dispositions and give time and space to teachers to think deeply about and develop these qualities. Hiring practices also need to discern candidates who are more likely to bring these traits to the profession from the beginning. This includes incorporating questions that explicitly ask candidates about how they intend to support a diverse student population. In addition, principals need to incorporate PD steeped in CRP and the student-centered approach of knowing students authentically. Lastly, principals need to be authorized to hold teachers accountable when they fail to treat diverse students with patience and understanding. This included being able to move them to a less diverse site where their disposition will be far less harmful. Doing this will empower teachers to be impactful change agents for the next generation, no matter which side of the tracks they are on.

APPENDIX A**EMPATHY INTERVIEW PROTOCOL**

Interview Protocol – First-Generation Latinx Student

Name of participant:

Graduating class of:

Interviewer:

Date:

Duration:

Location:

First of all, I want to thank you for your agreement to participate in this research study. I respect and value your time, and you have my commitment to honor the time frame we've agreed to. My name is Brandon Frank and I am a Doctoral student at California State University, Fullerton, and I'm pursuing my EDD in Educational Leadership. I live in Orange County and have worked for 17 years in the same school district.

Regarding this study I'm working on, I just want to take a moment to revisit the information I shared with you in preparation for this interview. I'm trying to understand, from the actual students' perspective, if there were any specific people, policies, or practices during your school experience that you found helpful. I want to focus on things that you think helped you be successful, both in school and in life more broadly and I also want to use the lens cultural background to enhance my understanding. The results of this study will help me to increase the presence of those aspects in my school site, my district, and maybe even beyond!

It's important to remember that during our conversation, there are absolutely no "right" or "wrong" answers. I really want to hear your honest thoughts and feelings about this topic. I

expect our conversation to last approximately 45 minutes, and everything you share with me will remain confidential.

As I mentioned, I would like to record our session to make sure that I can accurately reference your comments in my writing later. Thank you for signing the Informed Consent document prior to this interview.

Just as a general reminder about your rights as a participant: your participation is totally voluntary, and you can stop the interview at any time, refuse to answer any questions, or request that I stop the recorder for certain questions if you prefer.

Before we start, I want to take a moment to help you get to know me a bit better. I have been married for 23 years, I have two teenagers, and I am the first in my family to earn a college degree. As I mentioned, I've worked in the same district for 17 years now; 12 of those years were as a high school classroom teacher, 3 years as a middle school Assistant Principal, and I'm currently in my third year as an elementary school Principal. All of those years have been serving the same community of predominantly Latino families and students. I am now most interested in amplifying the voices of those I serve, and this research study is a major part of that pursuit.

I'd like to confirm some information about you as we begin. Remember, everything you share is completely confidential; no teachers or schools that you mention will be named in my dissertation. I'll ask you for a bit more information at the end of our conversation as well.

Name:

High School(s) attended:

ICEBREAKER

1. Let's start off with a memory. Can you tell me a positive memory you have from any

time in school? It can be about anything (academics, social life, family, etc.).

- a. Why do you think you still remember that? What makes it a “positive” memory for you?

SCHOOL EXPERIENCE

2. I want to ask you about your teachers specifically, and I want to focus on the cultural background of those who taught you in school. Do you remember having teachers that “looked like you,” or represented your own cultural background?

- a. For my data collection purposes, what is your best guess to the proportion or percentage of your teachers that represented your own cultural background?

3. Let’s talk about your experiences in classes led by educators who did not come from the same cultural background as you. Can you remember a time when you felt successful in school generally, or in a class specifically? Who or what made you feel that way?

- a. Are there any particular things you remember a teacher saying that helped you feel that way? Tell me about it, or if not, what do you wish you had heard?
- b. Were there any specific actions—grading policies or class rules, for example—that any of your teachers engaged in that helped you feel successful? Tell me about it, or if not, what do you wish they had done?

4. Let’s drill down on teachers more specifically. Can you tell me about a time when a teacher from a different cultural background “built you up?”

- a. How did that make you feel and what was the impact on you?
- b. Over your time in school, how many teachers do you think you had that truly “built you up?”
- c. Does that seem high or low to you? What do you think is the reason for that number?

5. Now let's pivot to discussing a challenge. Can you tell me about the hardest class you remember taking in school? What was so hard about it?

- a. Did that teacher do or say anything specifically to make the class seem easier? Harder?
- b. How did their words or actions impact you?

POLICY

6. Now I want to ask you about something a bit deeper. Did you ever feel like you didn't belong in a class? If so, what class was it and what was that like? If not, what class was it and what made you feel like you did belong?

- a. Did that teacher do or say anything specifically to make you feel that way? If so, what can you remember?

CONCLUDING QUESTIONS

7. Someday I will be using this research to help educators grow in their ability to serve diverse student populations, especially in predominantly Latino communities. What do you wish schools and non-Latino teachers knew about first-generation Latinx students?

- a. What qualities would you want administrators to look for when hiring teachers?
- b. What school or classroom actions--again, it could be grading policies, class rules, or expectations for example--would you want them to introduce or expand?

8. My ultimate goal is to amplify your voice with this research. Is there anything else you would want educators who "look like me" to know about how best to support first-generation Latinx students?

APPENDIX B

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

California State University, Fullerton Research Study Consent Form

Study Title: In Their Words: a Qualitative Study Exploring Belongingness and Positive Academic Outcomes for First-Generation Latinx Students

Protocol Number: HSR-22-23-376

Researcher: Brandon Frank, Doctoral Candidate, CSUF

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Brandon Frank, under the advisement of Dr. Huy Chung. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

This research study is being conducted to learn more about what qualities and characteristics, as well as which classroom policies and procedures, that first-generation Latinx students perceive as beneficial to their sense of belongingness and ability to be academically successful when possessed or implemented by their white teachers.

You are being asked to take part because you represent a particular group of former students who have graduated from a high school within the state of California and you have a valuable perspective that is worth knowing more about. The researcher intends to amplify the voices of students like you by performing this study.

Taking part in the study will take about 60 minutes in total. It is possible that the researcher may find a reason to ask additional questions at a later time, but this is optional. It would take about 30 minutes to complete any follow-up interview.

You can participate in this study if you are a first-generation Latinx student. In this study, first-generation means that neither of your parents earned a post-secondary degree in the United States, and Latinx means your ethnic ancestry connects to any of the countries in Latin America. In addition, you cannot take part in this study if you have not already graduated from high school.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the study, you will be asked to participate in an Empathy Interview in a one-on-one setting with the researcher. The interview can occur in person, but a virtual option will be made available for convenience. For virtual meetings, the researcher will create a Zoom link and share it via email communication prior to the interview. For in-person interviews a mutually agreed-upon neutral public space will be chosen. One hour will be set aside for the duration of your participation. By request,

a copy of the video or audio recording can be shared with you within one week of the interview. If the researcher determines that a follow-up interview is needed, the same procedure will be followed to schedule and meet for the interview, lasting approximately 30 minutes. The interview questions will ask you to reflect on your experiences as a student, including both positive and negative aspects of your experience. The questions are designed to elicit your honest feelings, and the interview protocol is built to secure mutual trust and respect. Your participation is completely voluntary, and you may refuse to ask any question at any time with no penalty of any kind. The video and audio recordings will be used exclusively for transcription purposes and can be shared with you upon request.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

There is unlikely to be a direct benefit to you from being in this study, however you may feel a sense of pride or satisfaction for your contribution to the furtherance of this scholarship and its potential positive impact on others. As we discover specific characteristics and practices that, according to the voices and stories of students themselves, can be shown to amplify the success of historically unsuccessful students who come from cultural marginalization and poverty, we can extend this insight to the vast and increasing numbers of Latinx students in schools across California and beyond.

School administrators can use evidence of effective practices to guide professional development and site level mission, vision, and practice; rank and file teachers can equally employ such evidence when looking for ways to increase success for their increasingly diverse student population. If the entire school team attempts to “paddle in the same direction” (here, in the form of reinforcing specific personal characteristics and implementing concrete pedagogical strategies campus wide), decisions will be guided by a common goal and will arguably be magnified through coherence, consistency, repetition and collective commitment. When an entire staff begins to live the creed that “all means all,” more students will benefit, and progress can be made on the long road to equity for students who come from limitations far outside of their control.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

The potential risks from taking part in this study are minimal, but could include some emotional or psychological stress when answering questions about your experiences and memories. The researcher has framed questions in a way to intentionally reduce the potential for such an experience but it may still occur.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study will be kept confidential to the extent allowed by law. No published results will identify you, and your name will not be associated with the findings. Under certain circumstances, information that identifies you may be released for internal and external reviews of this project. Data will be coded with a separate key that will be shared with inter-rater coders to create validity, but identifying information will not be part of the key. Participants’ privacy will be maintained at all times, as the researcher will not be sharing names with anyone and will maintain a naming convention using pseudonyms. All the data collected and maintained will be kept on a password protected computer. An audio recording will be made of all interviews in order to assist with transcription and coding afterward. You may ask for a copy of your audio recording at any time after the conclusion of the interview. In addition, if the interview needs to be performed virtually (ie: via Zoom), the video will also be recorded and maintained using the same protocol as all other notes and audio recordings. The only people with access to the data will be the researcher and the dissertation committee consisting of three expert

practitioners. They will only see collected information with pseudonyms and will not see your name attached to any of the data.

The results of this study may be published or presented at professional meetings, but the identities of all research participants will remain anonymous

The data for this study will be kept by the University for 5 years. The individual researcher may keep the data indefinitely. However, it would only be kept in order to revisit prior to any future professional presentation regarding this research study, and would remain confidential and protected by the same protocols used during the actual research process.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study.

As a show of appreciation, you will receive a \$5 Starbucks gift card for taking part in this study. If you decide to quit the study you will still receive the gift card if you started any part of the interview process. It will be handed to you at the conclusion of the interview, or mailed to you if you participate virtually (ie: via Zoom). If you are asked to return for an additional interview session, you will receive another gift card of the same value.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Brandon Frank, by email ██████@██████.org or by phone (████) █████-████. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu.

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or I have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form to keep.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

Your signature below indicates that you are giving permission to audio/video tape your responses.

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

REFERENCES

- Aggarwal, U. (2016). The ideological architecture of whiteness as property in educational policy. *Educational Policy*, 30(1), 128-152. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904815616486>
- Allen, K., Kern, M. L., Vella-Brodrick, D., Hattie, J., & Waters, L. (2016). What schools need to know about fostering school belonging: a meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(1), 1-34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-016-9389-8>
- Anyon, Y., Lechuga, C., Ortega, D., Downing, B., Greer, E., & Simmons, J. (2018). An exploration of the relationships between student racial background and the school sub-contexts of office discipline referrals: A critical race theory analysis. *Race, Ethnicity and Education*, 21(3), 390–406. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13613324.2017.1328594>
- AVID. (n.d.). *AVID | Closing the gap in education*. <http://www.avid.org>
- Banaji, M. R., & Hardin, C. D. (1996). Automatic stereotyping. *Psychological Science*, 7(3), 136-141. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.1996.tb00346.x>
- Beckert, J. (2010). Institutional isomorphism revisited: Convergence and divergence in institutional change. *Sociological Theory*, 28(2), 150–166. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9558.2010.01369.x>
- Bell, D. A. (1980). Brown v. Board of Education and the interest-convergence dilemma. *Harvard Law Review*, 93(3), 518-533. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1340546>
- Benner, A. D., & Graham, S. (2011). Latino adolescents' experiences of discrimination across the first 2 years of high school: Correlates and influences on educational outcomes. *Child Development*, 82(2), 508-519. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01524.x>
- Bernal, G., & Domenech Rodríguez, M. M. (2009). Advances in Latino family research: Cultural adaptations of evidence-based interventions. *Family Process*, 48(2), 169-178. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1545-5300.2009.01275.x>
- California Department of Education. (2023, April 5). *Certificated staff by ethnicity 2018-2019*. <https://dq.cde.ca.gov/dataquest/Staff/StaffByEth.aspx?cLevel=State&cYear=2018-19&cChoice=StateNum&cType=O&cGender=B&Submit=1>
- Chavez, M. L., Soriano, M., & Oliverez, P. (2007). Undocumented students' access to college: The American dream denied. *Latino Studies*, 5(2), 254–263. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.lst.8600255>
- Chetty, R., Friedman, J. N., & Rockoff, J. E. (2014). Measuring the impacts of teachers II: Teacher value-added and student outcomes in adulthood. *The American Economic Review*, 104(9), 2633-2679. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.104.9.2633>
- Choy, S. P. (2001). *Students whose parents did not go to college: postsecondary access, persistence, and attainment*. National Center for Education Statistics, U.S. Dept. of Education, Office of Educational Research and Improvement.
- Cole, M. (2009). *Critical Race Theory and education: A Marxist response* (1st ed.). Palgrave Macmillan.

- Collins, J. (2009). Social reproduction in classrooms and schools. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 38(1), 33-48. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.anthro.37.081407.085242>
- Conchas, G. Q. (2001). Structuring failure and success: Understanding the variability in Latino school engagement. *Harvard Educational Review*, 71(3), 475–504. <https://doi.org/10.17763/haer.71.3.280w814v1603473k>
- Corbin, J., & Strauss, A. (1990). Grounded theory research: Procedures, canons, and evaluative criteria. *Qualitative Sociology*, 13(1), 3–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00988593>
- Cortese, L. (2011). Teachers and ‘resting routines’: Reflections on cognitive justice, inclusion and the pedagogy of poverty. *Improving Schools*, 14(3), 258–267. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1365480211422284>
- Creswell, J. W., Creswell, J. W., & Guetterman, T. C. (2021). *Educational research: planning, conducting and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (6th ed., global edition.). Pearson.
- Dearing, E., Walsh, M. E., Sibley, E., Lee-St. John, T., Foley, C., & Raczek, A. E. (2016). Can community and school-based supports improve the achievement of first-generation immigrant children attending high-poverty schools? *Child Development*, 87(3), 883–897. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12507>
- Delgado, V. (2020). Children of immigrants as “brokers” in an era of exclusion. *Sociology Compass*, 14(10), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1111/soc4.12832>
- Devine, P. G., Forscher, P. S., Austin, A. J., & Cox, W. T. L. (2012). Long-term reduction in implicit race bias: A prejudice habit-breaking intervention. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 48(6), 1267-1278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2012.06.003>
- Domenech Rodríguez, M. M., Donovan, M. R., & Crowley, S. L. (2009). Parenting styles in a cultural context: Observations of “protective parenting” in first-generation Latinos. *Family Process*, 48(2), 195–210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1545-5300.2009.01277.x>
- Dovidio, J. F., & Gaertner, S. L. (2000). Aversive racism and selection decisions: 1989 and 1999. *Psychological Science*, 11(4), 315-319. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9280.00262>
- Dovidio, J. F., Gluszek, A., John, M.-S., Dittmann, R., & Lagunes, P. (2010). Understanding bias toward Latinos: Discrimination, dimensions of difference, and experience of exclusion. *Journal of Social Issues*, 66(1), 59-78. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4560.2009.01633.x>
- Drake, C. (2006). Turning points: Using teachers’ mathematics life stories to understand the implementation of mathematics education reform. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*, 9(6), 579–608. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10857-006-9021-9>
- Duckworth, A. (2019). *Grit - Character lab*. <https://doi.org/10.53776/playbooks-grit>
- Duncan, G. J., & Murnane, R. J. (2016). Rising inequality in family incomes and children’s educational outcomes. *RSF: Russell Sage Foundation Journal of the Social Sciences*, 2(2), 142–158. <https://doi.org/10.7758/rsf.2016.2.2.06>

- Edwards, K. E. (2006). Aspiring social justice ally identity development: A conceptual model. *NASPA Journal*, 43(4), 39-60. <https://doi.org/10.2202/1949-6605.1722>
- “Ensuring Fair and Reliable Measures of Effective Teaching: Culminating findings from the MET project's three-year study.” (2013). *The Education Digest*, 78(8), 59.
- Farkas, G. (2003). Racial disparities and discrimination in education: What do we know, how do we know it, and what do we need to know? *Teachers College Record (1970)*, 105(6), 1119–1146. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9620.00279>
- Feliciano, P. (2000). Punto final! A “new wave” of Latino college students. *The Hispanic Outlook in Higher Education*, 10(25), 76.
- Fiske, S. T., Cuddy, A. J. C., Glick, P., & Xu, J. (2002). A model of (often mixed) stereotype content: Competence and warmth respectively follow from perceived status and competition. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 82(6), 878-902. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.82.6.878>
- Friedrich, A., Flunger, B., Nagengast, B., Jonkmann, K., & Trautwein, U. (2015). Pygmalion effects in the classroom: Teacher expectancy effects on students' math achievement. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 41, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2014.10.006>
- Gándara, P., & Contreras, F. (2020). *The Latino education crisis*. Harvard University Press.
- Garcia-Reid, P., Peterson, C. H., & Reid, R. J. (2015). Parent and teacher support among Latino immigrant youth: Effects on school engagement and school trouble avoidance. *Education and Urban Society*, 47(3), 328-343. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013124513495278>
- Garza, R. (2009). Latino and white high school students' perceptions of caring behaviors. *Urban Education*, 44(3), 297–321. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085908318714>
- Gee, J. P. (2012). *Social linguistics and literacies: ideology in discourses* (4th ed.). Routledge.
- Gillborn, D. (2005). Education policy as an act of white supremacy: whiteness, critical race theory and education reform. *Journal of Education Policy*, 20(4), 485-506. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680930500132346>
- Gregg, P., Macmillan, L., & Vittori, C. (2019). Intergenerational income mobility: access to top jobs, the low-pay no-pay cycle and the role of education in a common framework. *Journal of Population Economics*, 32(2), 501-528. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00148-018-0722-z>
- Gudiño, O. (2013). Behavioral inhibition and risk for posttraumatic stress symptoms in Latino children exposed to violence. *An Official Publication of the International Society for Research in Child and Adolescent Psychopathology*, 41(6), 983-992. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10802-013-9731-2>
- Gurantz, O., Hurwitz, M., & Smith, J. (2017). Boosting Hispanic college completion. *Education Next*, 17(3), 61.
- Guyll, M., Madon, S., Prieto, L., & Scherr, K. C. (2010). The potential roles of self-fulfilling prophecies, stigma consciousness, and stereotype threat in linking Latino/a ethnicity and educational outcomes. *Journal of Social Issues*, 66(1), 113-130. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4560.2009.01636.x>

- Haberman, M. (1991). The pedagogy of poverty versus good teaching. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 73(4), 290–294.
- Harris, C. I. (1993). Whiteness as property. *Harvard Law Review*, 106(8), 1709.
- Hernandez, J. C., & Lopez, M. A. (2004). Leaking pipeline: Issues impacting Latino/a college student retention. *Journal of College Student Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, 6(1), 37-60. <https://doi.org/10.2190/FBLY-0UAF-EE7W-QJD2>
- Holdsworth Center. (2020, August 18). *How to do empathy interviews with students* [video]. <https://holdsworthcenter.org/blog/how-to-do-empathy-interviews-with-students/>
- Horn, L., Nuñez, A.-M., & Bobbitt, L. G. (2000). *Mapping the road to college: First-generation students' math track, planning strategies, and context of support*. U.S. Dept. of Education, Office of Educational Research and Improvement.
- Howe, K. R. (1997). *Understanding equal educational opportunity: Social justice, democracy, and schooling*. Teachers College Press.
- Jaap, N., & Pieter, H. (2016). The association between neighbourhoods and educational achievement, a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 31(2), 321-347. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-015-9460-7>
- James, S. C. (1988). Social capital in the creation of human capital. *American Journal of Sociology*, 94, S95-S120. <https://doi.org/10.1086/228943>
- James, S. L., & Amato, P. R. (2013). Self-esteem and the reproduction of social class. *Social Science Quarterly*, 94(4), 933-955. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ssqu.12019>
- Jens, B. (2010). Institutional isomorphism revisited: Convergence and divergence in institutional change. *Sociological Theory*, 28(2), 150-166. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9558.2010.01369.x>
- Kang, S. K., & Bodenhausen, G. V. (2015). Multiple identities in social perception and interaction: Challenges and opportunities. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 66(1), 547-574. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010814-015025>
- Kluger, A. N., & Nir, D. (2010). The feedforward interview. *Human Resource Management Review*, 20(3), 235-246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2009.08.002>
- Kohli, R., & Pizarro, M. (2016). Fighting to educate our own: Teachers of color, relational accountability, and the struggle for racial justice. *Equity & Excellence in Education*, 49(1), 72–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10665684.2015.1121457>
- Ladson-Billings, G. (1998). Just what is critical race theory and what's it doing in a nice field like education? *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 11(1), 7-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/095183998236863>
- Lareau, A. (2003). *Unequal childhoods: class, race, and family life*. University of California Press.

- Lee, T. L., & Fiske, S. T. (2006). Not an outgroup, not yet an ingroup: Immigrants in the Stereotype Content Model. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 30(6), 751-768. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2006.06.005>
- Leonardo, Z. (2013). The color of supremacy: Beyond the discourse of 'white privilege'. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 36(2), 137-152. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-5812.2004.00057.x>
- López, F. A. (2016). Culturally responsive pedagogies in Arizona and Latino students' achievement. *Teachers College Record (1970)*, 118(5), 1.
- Lynn, M., & Jennings, M. E. (2009). Power, politics, and critical race pedagogy: A critical race analysis of Black male teachers' pedagogy. *Race Ethnicity and Education: Critical Race Praxis*, 12(2), 173-196. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13613320902995467>
- Martinez, J. A., Sher, K. J., Krull, J. L., & Wood, P. K. (2009). Blue-collar scholars?: Mediators and moderators of university attrition in first-generation college students. *Journal of College Student Development*, 50(1), 87-103. <https://doi.org/10.1353/csd.0.0053>
- Matias, C. E., Montoya, R., & Nishi, N. W. M. (2016). Blocking CRT: How the emotionality of whiteness blocks CRT in urban teacher education. *Educational Studies (Ames)*, 52(1), 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131946.2015.1120205>
- Maxwell, J. a. (2023). *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach* (4th ed., vol. 41). Sage Publications, Inc.
- McNutt, J. G., Queiro-Tajalli, I., Boland, K. M., & Campbell, C. (2001). Information poverty and the Latino community: Implications for social work practice and social work education. *Journal of Ethnic & Cultural Diversity in Social Work*, 10(4), 1-20. https://doi.org/10.1300/J051v10n04_01
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldaña, J. (2014). *Qualitative data analysis: A methods sourcebook* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Moreno, R. (2021). The guilt of success: Looking at Latino first-generation college students' experience of leaving home. *Journal of Hispanic Higher Education*, 20(2), 213-231. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1538192719849756>
- Moses, M. S. (2002). *Embracing race: Why we need race-conscious education policy*. Teachers College Press.
- Murnane, R. J. (2013). US high school graduation rates: Patterns and explanations. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 51(2), 370-422. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.51.2.370>
- Niehaus, K., & Kumpiene, G. (2014). Language brokering and self-concept: An exploratory study of Latino students' experiences in middle and high school. *Hispanic Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 36(2), 124-143. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739986314524166>
- Nuñez, A.-M., Hoover, R. E., Pickett, K., Stuart-Carruthers, A. C., & Vázquez, M. (2013). *Latinos in higher education and Hispanic-serving institutions: Creating conditions for success*. Jossey-Bass.

- O'Neal, C. W., Richardson, E. W., Mancini, J. A., & Grimsley, R. N. (2016). Parents' early life stressful experiences, their present well-being, and that of their children. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 86(4), 425-435. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ort0000140>
- Osayande, E. X. (n.d.). *Word to the wise: Unpacking the white privilege of Tim Wise*. People of Color Organize. <http://www.peopleofcolororganize.com/analysis/word-wise-unpacking-white-privilege-tim-wise/>
- Owens, A. (2018). Income segregation between school districts and inequality in students' achievement. *Sociology of Education*, 91(1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038040717741180>
- Papay, J. P., Murnane, R. J., & Willett, J. B. (2015). Income-based inequality in educational outcomes: Learning from state longitudinal data systems. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 37(1S), 29S–52S. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0162373715576364>
- Patton, L. D., & Bondi, S. (2015). Nice white men or social justice allies?: Using critical race theory to examine how white male faculty and administrators engage in ally work. *Race Ethnicity and Education*, 18(4), 488-514. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13613324.2014.1000289>
- Payne, B. K. (2001). Prejudice and perception: The role of automatic and controlled processes in misperceiving a weapon. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 81(2), 181-192. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.81.2.181>
- Peguerro, A. A., & Shekarkhar, Z. (2011). Latino/a student misbehavior and school punishment. *Hispanic Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 33(1), 54–70. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739986310388021>
- Perez, S. A. (2000). An ethic of caring in teaching culturally diverse students. *Education*, 121(1), 102–102.
- Peshkin, A. (1988). In search of subjectivity—One's own. *Educational Researcher*, 17(7), 17-21. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X017007017>
- Petty, T. (2014). Motivating first-generation students to academic success and college completion. *College Student Journal*, 48(2), 257-264.
- Pew Research Center. (2016, April 19). *Statistical portrait of Hispanics in the United States*. Pew Research Center Hispanic Trends: www.pewhispanic.org/2016/04/19/statistical-portrait-of-hispanics-in-the-unitedstates/ph_2016_stat-portrait-hispanic-current-04
- Pfeffer, F. T. (2018). Growing wealth gaps in education. *Demography*, 55(3), 1033–1068. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13524-018-0666-7>
- Portes, A., & MacLeod, D. (1996). Educational progress of children of immigrants: The roles of class, ethnicity, and school context. *Sociology of Education*, 69(4), 255-275. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2112714>
- Ratcliffe, C. (2015). *Child poverty and adult success*. Urban Institute. <https://www.urban.org/research/publication/child-poverty-and-adult-success>
- Richard, D., & Jean, S. (2017). *Critical race theory: An introduction* (3rd ed.). NYU Press.

- Rockoff, J. E., Jacob, B. A., Kane, T. J., & Staiger, D. O. (2011). Can you recognize an effective teacher when you recruit one? *Education Finance and Policy*, 6(1), 43-74.
https://doi.org/10.1162/edfp_a_00022
- Rosenthal, R. (1987). Pygmalion effects: Existence, magnitude, and social importance. *Educational Researcher*, 16(9), 37-40. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X016009037>
- Rothstein, J. (2019). Inequality of educational opportunity? *Journal of Labor Economics*, 37(S1), S85–S123. <https://doi.org/10.1086/700888>
- Rubin, H. J. & Rubin, I. S. (2012). *Qualitative interviewing: The art of hearing data* (3rd ed.). Sage.
- Ruíz, R. (1984). Orientations in language planning. *NABE Journal*, 8(2), 15-34.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08855072.1984.10668464>
- Saenz, V. B. (2007). *First in my Family: A profile of first-generation college students at four-year institutions since 1971*. Cooperative Institutional Research Program, Higher Education Research Institute.
- Santiago, C. D., & Wadsworth, M. E. (2011). Family and cultural influences on low-income Latino children's adjustment. *Journal of Clinical Child and Adolescent Psychology*, 40(2), 332-337.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15374416.2011.546038>
- Sardoc, M. (2018). Democratic education at 30: An interview with Dr. Amy Gutmann. *Theory and Research in Education*, 16(2), 244-252. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477878518774087>
- Sibley, E., & Brabeck, K. (2017). Latino immigrant students' school experiences in the United States: The importance of family-school–community collaborations. *School Community Journal*, 27(1), 137-158.
- Skiba, R. J, Horner, R. H., Chung, C-G., Rausch, M. K., May, S.L, & Tobin, T. (2011). Race is not neutral: A national investigation of African American and Latino disproportionality in school discipline. *School Psychology Review*, 40(1), 85–107.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02796015.2011.12087730>
- Sólorzano, D. G., Villalpando, O., & Oseguera, L. (2005). Educational inequities and Latina/o undergraduate students in the United States: A critical race analysis of their educational progress. *Journal of Hispanic Higher Education*, 4(3), 272–294.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1538192705276550>
- Straubhaar, R. (2016). Acknowledging and interrogating the place of race and privilege in comparative and international education. *Annual Review of Comparative and International Education* 2016, 30, 71-79. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1479-367920160000030006>
- Thiede, B. C., & Brooks, M. M. (2018). Child poverty across immigrant generations in the United States, 1993–2016. *Demographic Research*, 39, 1065–1080.
<https://doi.org/10.4054/DemRes.2018.39.40>
- Thompson, A. (2003). Tiffany, friend of people of color: White investments in antiracism. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 16(1), 7-29.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0951839032000033509>

- Turcios-Cotto, V. Y., & Milan, S. (2013). Racial/Ethnic differences in the educational expectations of adolescents: Does pursuing higher education mean something different to Latino students compared to White and Black students? *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, *42*(9), 1399–1412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-012-9845-9>
- Toutkoushian, R. K., Hossler, D., & McCall, B. P. (2015). The effect of participating in Indiana's twenty-first century scholars program on college enrollments. *Review of Higher Education*, *39*(1), 59-95. <https://doi.org/10.1353/rhe.2015.0042>
- Vallier, K. (2019). Rawls, Piketty, and the critique of welfare-state capitalism. *The Journal of Politics*, *81*(1), 142–152. <https://doi.org/10.1086/700108>
- van den Bergh, L., Denessen, E., Hornstra, L., Voeten, M., & Holland, R. W. (2010). The implicit prejudiced attitudes of teachers: Relations to teacher expectations and the ethnic achievement gap. *American Educational Research Journal*, *47*(2), 497-527. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831209353594>
- Vaught, S. E., & Castagno, A. E. (2008). "I don't think I'm a racist": Critical race theory, teacher attitudes, and structural racism. *Race Ethnicity and Education*, *11*(2), 95-113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13613320802110217>
- Welch, K., & Payne, A. A. (2018). Latino/a student threat and school disciplinary policies and practices. *Sociology of Education*, *91*(2), 91–110. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038040718757720>
- Wiley, T. G., & Wright, W. E. (2004). Against the undertow: Language-minority education policy and politics in the “age of accountability”. *Educational Policy*, *18*(1), 142-168. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904803260030>
- Will, K., & Wayne, N. (1994). Return of the citizen: A survey of recent work on citizenship theory. *Ethics*, *104*(2), 352-381. <https://doi.org/10.1086/293605>
- Yoshikawa, H., Aber, J. L., & Beardslee, W. R. (2012). The effects of poverty on the mental, emotional, and behavioral health of children and youth. *The American Psychologist*, *67*(4), 272–284. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0028015>
- Zyngier, D. (2017). Left numb and unengaged. (Re)conceptualising risk: What (seems to) work for at-risk students. *Social Sciences (Basel)*, *6*(1), 32. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci6010032>